

GECH Pīnyīn for Chinese Language Education in Ethiopia

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Abstract

This study explores the potential integration of the Ge'ez/Amharic writing system into Chinese-language instruction as a means to enhance Ethiopian learners' comprehension of Mandarin. The Amharic script—commonly referred to as Fidel—is derived from the ancient Ge'ez script and functions as a syllabic writing system. Since Amharic is serving as the working language of the Ethiopian federal government, this script remains widely familiar to millions of Ethiopians. In this study, the terms Ge'ez, Amharic, and Fidel are used interchangeably to denote Ethiopia's traditional writing system. By examining the compatibility of tones between the Ge'ez script and Mandarin language, this research seeks to identify the possibility of studying Chinese by Geez script. Ultimately, the goal is to accelerate Chinese language acquisition and improving learning outcomes.

The study presents the development of a Ge'ez-based phonetic transcription system comparable to Hànyǔ Pīnyīn. This innovation, termed GECH Pīnyīn, derives its name from the first two initial letters of “Ge'ez” and “Chinese.” GECH Pīnyīn employs Ge'ez/Amharic characters to represent the four tones of Mandarin pronunciation, thereby adapting the Amharic writing system to the phonological structure of Mandarin Chinese. It integrates Ge'ez script with Chinese tonal diacritics to form a hybrid transcription system.

Based on serious analysis in phonetics, cross-linguistic transfer theory, and sinological studies, the paper synthesizes existing researches, identifies major research gaps, and proposes future study. Furthermore, by studying the parallel between Ge'ez melodic notation and the tonal system of Mandarin, the study demonstrates that Ethiopia's native linguistic knowledge can be helpful as a cognitive bridge for understanding tones.

This study holds substantial implications for Chinese studies in non-Latin script contexts. It offers the potential to enable millions of learners to access Mandarin through their native writing systems, rather than relying exclusively on Latin-script-mediated approaches.

Keywords: Geez, Chinese Phonology, Pīnyīn, Ethio-China Linguistic Relations

1 Introduction

Ethiopia and China share rich historical legacies as two of the world's oldest civilizations. China's recorded history spans more than 5,000 years, while Ethiopia's extends over 3,000 years (Melaku, 2023). As ancient societies, both developed distinct writing systems—China through the Hanzi script and Ethiopia through the Ge'ez/Amharic script. This study seeks to integrate elements of these writing and reading traditions to develop more effective approaches for learning the Chinese language in Ethiopia.

With a population exceeding 130 million Ethiopia is the second most populous country in Africa. China is Ethiopia's largest trading partner and leading infrastructure developer. Parallel to stronger political, economic and cultural relations between Ethiopia and China, the demand for Chinese language proficiency among Ethiopians has grown significantly. Chinese has consequently emerged as a strategic medium of communication for trade, investment, educational exchange, and cultural diplomacy. It is also one of the prominent working languages of the United Nations Organizations (Tonkin, 2011). However, a persistent pedagogical gap—stemming from reliance on the Latin alphabet-based Hànyǔ Pīnyīn system—continues to hinder effective Chinese language acquisition in Ethiopia.

Ethiopia's distinctive linguistic landscape—particularly the Amharic language, which is written in a script derived from Ge'ez—is identified in this study as offering significant advantages for Chinese language education. The standard Hànyǔ Pīnyīn system functions as a Latin-based phonetic transcription tool for Mandarin Chinese; it is fundamentally designed for learners with prior familiarity with the Roman alphabet (Liu, 2009). For Amharic speakers, whose literacy is rooted in a fundamentally different writing tradition—syllabic rather than alphabetic—the simultaneous demands of learning Chinese phonology, mastering its four lexical tones, and navigating a Roman-based transcription system impose significant cognitive burdens, thereby hindering the language acquisition process.

As Lina Ayenew observed in her pioneering work "DALU," (Lina, 2016) many Ethiopian students give up studying Chinese language after a few weeks of study "because the Chinese transliteration system is difficult to learn and there is a disconnection between the lessons and

their daily lives." (Lina, 2016). Although Latin letters are widely used globally, they do not carry intrinsic phonetic meaning for Amharic speakers accustomed to processing the consonant–vowel syllabic structure of Fidel. To address this fundamental mismatch, the present study proposes a systematic alternative: the development of a comprehensive Mandarin Chinese phonetic transcription system based on Ge'ez/Amharic Fidel, incorporating integrated tonal markers.

2 Statement of the Problem

Ethiopia's deepening economic, diplomatic, and educational partnership with China has generated unprecedented demand for Mandarin Chinese proficiency among Ethiopian learners. China is Ethiopia's largest trading partner and a primary destination for higher education. Thus Chinese language skills have become essential for trade, investment, technology transfer, and cultural exchange. However, Chinese language acquisition in Ethiopia faces a persistent and fundamental barrier: the reliance on Hànyǔ Pīnyīn, a Latin-based phonetic transcription system that conflicts with Ethiopia's indigenous writing tradition.

Amharic, the working language of the Ethiopian federal government, employs the Ge'ez/Amharic Fidel—a syllabic writing system where each character represents a consonant-vowel unit. This structural mismatch between Geez and Latin creates what this study terms "double mediation": Ethiopian learners must navigate Chinese phonology through the phonetic framework of Latin letters, often filtered through English pronunciation habits, before accessing Mandarin sounds. The cognitive burden imposed by this indirect pathway significantly impedes accurate pronunciation acquisition, contributing to high dropout rates and persistent pronunciation errors among Ethiopian Chinese language learners.

Existing resources designed for Amharic-speaking learners have failed to address the most critical feature of Mandarin Chinese: its four lexical tones. The pioneering textbook called DALU (Lina, 2016) successfully demonstrated that Amharic Fidel can represent Chinese sounds more accurately than English letters, yet it omitted any system for indicating tones. Similarly, the Commercial Press Chinese Visual Dictionary (2017) provides vocabulary with Amharic translations but lacks tonal notation entirely. This omission is not a minor pedagogical oversight but a fundamental flaw, as tone distinguishes meaning in Chinese—without systematic tonal

representation, learners cannot differentiate words such as mā (mother), má (hemp), mǎ (horse), and mà (scold). The absence of tonal markers in Amharic-script resources actively promotes negative cross-linguistic transfer, causing learners to default to their non-tonal native language phonological framework and cause pronunciation errors that become increasingly difficult to correct over time.

This study addresses the critical gap by developing GECH Pīnyīn—a systematic Chinese phonetic transcription system based on Ge'ez/Amharic Fidel that integrates tonal markers directly into the script. The system leverages the syllabic structure of Fidel, which naturally aligns with Mandarin's patterns, while adapting the melodic sounds from Ethiopia's indigenous Zema tradition that helps to represent Mandarin tones. By enabling Ethiopian learners to access Chinese pronunciation directly through their native writing system without English phonetic interference, this approach eliminates the "double mediation" barrier and transforms tone acquisition.

However, despite its theoretical promise, the scholarly foundation for this innovation remains embryonic. This study therefore seeks to establish the linguistic principles underlying Amharic-Chinese phonological mapping, develop a comprehensive tonal marking system integrated with Fidel, and propose a research agenda for experimental validation and resource development that can transform Chinese language education in Ethiopia and serve as a replicable model for indigenous script-based language learning worldwide.

3 Theoretical Frameworks

Rooted in second language acquisition (SLA) research, Cross-Linguistic Transfer Theory examines how a learner's native language (L1) influences the acquisition of a second language (L2). According to this framework, learners tend to transfer the forms, meanings, and distributions of their first language to the target language. This influence may be either positive (facilitative) or negative (interferential). Positive transfer occurs when structures, sounds, or conceptual categories in the L1 align with those in the L2, thereby accelerating learning and reducing cognitive effort. In contrast, negative transfer, or interference, arises when differences

between the two languages result in predictable errors and processing difficulties (Jarvis et al., 2008).

Cross-Linguistic Transfer Theory provides a critical lens through which to analyze the cognitive and pedagogical challenges encountered by Ethiopian learners of Chinese. Geez/Amharic and Chinese are typologically distant languages, belonging to separate language families- Semitic and Sinitic, (Dong, 2020) respectively and possessing fundamentally different phonological, grammatical, and orthographic structures. This typological distance creates a complex landscape for transfer, wherein opportunities for positive transfer are initially limited due to the scarcity of shared structural features.

However, the present study focuses on a specific pedagogical intervention: the use of the Amharic *Fidel* script as a phonetic bridge for transcribing Chinese sounds. From the perspective of Cross-Linguistic Transfer Theory, this approach strategically leverages learners' existing L1 orthographic knowledge to facilitate L2 phonological acquisition. By employing a familiar script—the Amharic *Fidel*—rather than introducing an entirely new writing system, such as Chinese characters or even the Roman-based *Pīnyīn*, the intervention seeks to reduce cognitive load. This enables learners to draw on their established knowledge of *Fidel* and focus more intensively on the features of Chinese phonology.

Within the framework of Cross-Linguistic Transfer Theory, if a phonetic transcription system fails to visually encode tones, learners are likely to default to their L1 phonological framework, thereby perpetuating fundamental errors. The present study therefore employs Cross-Linguistic Transfer Theory to argue that the omission of tonal marking in existing resources is not a minor pedagogical oversight, but a critical flaw that actively promotes negative transfer. Conversely, the deliberate and systematic inclusion of tonal markers within the Amharic *Fidel* script is expected to foster positive transfer. In this sense, the proposed transcription system functions as a transfer-enhancing tool, effectively bridging the typological gap between a non-tonal L1 and a tonal L2.

4 Literature Review

The foundational work in the domain of Chinese phonetic transcription using the Amharic Fidel script is the textbook titled DALU, prepared by Lina Getachew Ayenew (Lina, 2016). The attempt is a good start. However, it has a significant limitation. What distinguishes DALU from the current study is that her study lacks symbols representing the four Chinese writing tones on the Geez alphabet/ Fidel. As Lina Getachew described in depth, "Amharic Fidel captures Chinese sounds better than English letters," (Lina, 2016) suggesting that the Amharic phonetic inventory provides more correspondences for Mandarin phonology than Latin letters, which have English pronunciation tendencies.

However, the present research distinguishes itself from previous works through one key innovation: the systematic inclusion of tonal marking within the *Ge'ez/Fidel* writing system. While *DALU* and subsequent resources, such as the *Commercial Press Chinese Visual Dictionary*, successfully demonstrated the representation of Chinese words in Amharic *Fidel*, they did not provide a method for indicating the four Mandarin tones. Without tonal marks, accurate use of Chinese phonology is not possible. This study introduces a comprehensive tonal marking system specifically designed to integrate with the visual and structural features of *Ge'ez/Fidel*. This represents a novel innovation—the first of its kind—by combining standard *Pīnyīn* tonal marks with Ethiopia's indigenous *Ge'ez* script.

Absence of tone marks on the Geez script is not unique to DALU but is echoed in other available resources designed for Amharic-speaking learners. The Chinese Visual Dictionary, published by the Commercial Press, (The Commercial Press, 2017) provides a collection of 1,400 frequently used Chinese words accompanied by their Amharic translations. While valuable for vocabulary acquisition, this visual dictionary, much like DALU, similarly omits tonal notation on the Geez/Amharic Fidel script, perpetuating the gap in comprehensive phonetic representation.

A broader examination of related studies on non-Latin phonetic transcription systems reveals successful precedents for adapting scripts to represent Chinese sounds. Historical and contemporary examples, such as the Xiao'erjing system—which represents Chinese sounds using the Arabic script—and the Dungan Cyrillic alphabet, (Hussain et al., 2016) demonstrate

that non-Latin scripts can be effectively employed for Chinese phonetic transcription. These cases provide clear evidence that the absence of tonal markings in Amharic and other non-Latin scripts has created significant challenges for accurate pronunciation.

5 Research Objectives

This comprehensive study has the following interrelated objectives:

- Conduct a rigorous comparative analysis of the Ge’ez/Amharic and Mandarin phonetic systems, identifying systematic correspondences and points of divergence that must be addressed in the transcription design.
- Establish scientifically grounded correspondences between Ge’ez/Amharic Fidel and Mandarin phonemes (initials, finals, and tones) to maximize pedagogical effectiveness.
- Develop and present a standardized system for representing Mandarin tones using symbols that align with the visual structure of Ge’ez/Amharic Fidel, maintain clarity, and avoid conflicts with existing Amharic vowel marks.
- Prepare a comprehensive framework for future empirical research, including preparing bilingual dictionary, training module & cultural text books, experimental validation studies, and digital tool development initiatives.

6 Justification of the Study

The deepening of Ethiopia–China relations has extended beyond infrastructure and trade into the realms of human capital and cultural exchange. In the context of Chinese language education in Ethiopia, a significant barrier remains: the “double mediation” of the Chinese language through the Latin alphabet via Hànyǔ Pīnyīn (Koskinen, 2021). This research aims to bridge this gap by establishing a systematic, indigenous phonetic framework. By utilizing the Amharic Fidel—a script already mastered by millions of Ethiopians—this study proposes a pedagogical innovation that makes Mandarin Chinese accessible, intuitive, and culturally resonant for Ethiopian learners.

Currently, Pīnyīn serves as the global standard but was designed for learners familiar with the Latin alphabet. For Amharic speakers, it acts as a “third-party” barrier. Most Ethiopians learn English before Chinese, which introduces phonetic interference. For instance the letter X and Q of English do not have the same sound for Chinese language.

Standard Pīnyīn requires Amharic speakers to first navigate the phonetic rules of the English alphabet before accessing Mandarin sounds. Unlike the Latin alphabet, which is phonemic, Ge'ez/Amharic Fidel is fundamentally syllabic. When an Ethiopian student sees the word ሙገ, the brain processes it as a single unit of sound. By contrast, when processing “Ma” in Pīnyīn, the learner must blend two separate units (M + a). Using Fidel, the cognitive processing of Chinese aligns naturally with the learner’s established literacy patterns, creating a 1:1 visual-to-sound correspondence. This reduces cognitive load, allowing learners to focus fully on Mandarin phonology. The Amharic script is phonetically rich enough to cover all Mandarin sounds, with 33 consonants and 7 vowels, (Abate et al., 2005). It is superior in many ways to the Latin alphabet, which has only 26 letters and 5 vowels (Dickerson, 2006). Fidel can represent Mandarin’s distinct sounds with precision, and unlike English, both Amharic and Mandarin employ similar articulatory mechanisms involving the throat and glottis.

Mandarin is a tonal language, yet many learners struggle to visualize pitch. Historical adaptations, such as Xiao'erjing (using the Arabic script) and the Dungan Cyrillic alphabet, exist, but neither system encodes tones. This research introduces a groundbreaking innovation by adapting the Ge'ez reading system—specifically its melodic marks—to represent Mandarin tones. By integrating tonal symbols (¯, ´, ˇ, `) directly onto the script, this system provides a visual “roadmap” for pitch. The four Mandarin tones are transformed from abstract concepts into visible, readable instructions, leveraging learners’ familiarity with Ethiopian liturgical and poetic rhythms.

While the Ge'ez script is exceptionally well-suited for this task due to its built-in vowel system, a few Mandarin sounds—such as “ü”—require the creation of unique letters. This approach mirrors historical precedents, like Xiao'erjing, where new characters were developed specifically for Chinese sounds. As China remains Ethiopia’s primary economic partner, the demand for a Mandarin-literate workforce in technical, diplomatic, and commercial sectors is at an all-time high. A Ge'ez/Amharic-based system has the potential to drastically reduce the high dropout rates in traditional Mandarin courses by making the early stages of learning less intimidating. This research asserts Ethiopia’s “script sovereignty,” demonstrating that Ge'ez—one of the world’s oldest living writing systems—is a modern, flexible tool capable of engaging with the world’s most spoken languages. Using Ge'ez dignifies the learning process by framing Mandarin

as an equal partner to Ethiopian culture rather than filtering it through a third language-Latin. This approach increases learner motivation and cultural engagement, factors that are scientifically proven to improve retention.

The goal of this research is not merely translation but empowerment: it positions Ethiopia's indigenous scripts to fill the gaps left by Pīnyīn. By removing the Latin intermediary, learners gain a direct “linguistic bridge” to Chinese. This framework lays the foundation for a new era of South-South cooperation, where technology and education are delivered through indigenous systems, fostering a generation of professionals who are both globally competent and culturally grounded.

7 Significance of the Study

China, the world's second-largest economy with a population of approximately 1.4 billion, is one of the most influential global actors and a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council. Proficiency in Chinese therefore offers substantial strategic advantages. With one of the most extensive diplomatic networks worldwide, China maintains deep and expanding relations with numerous countries. A significant number of Chinese professionals work across various sectors in Ethiopia, while many Ethiopian students pursue higher education in China. Enhancing Chinese language proficiency is critical for strengthening political, economic, and cultural ties, as well as for facilitating knowledge and technology transfer to Ethiopia.

This research offers substantial practical value for Ethiopia by addressing persistent communication challenges. The government's strong emphasis on infrastructure development, foreign direct investment, international trade, and technology transfer—areas closely linked to Chinese partnerships—demands a workforce equipped with foundational Chinese language skills. Simultaneously, the growing number of Ethiopian students pursuing higher education in China, underscores the need for more effective preparatory language training. Providing Chinese instruction supported by Ge'ez/Amharic Fidel, rather than relying solely on the Latin-based Pīnyīn, would enable learners to develop stronger reading and comprehension skills before departing for study in China.

8 Scope of the Study

Countries such as Ethiopia, which possess their own indigenous writing systems, need not rely exclusively on English letters or the Hànyǔ Pīnyīn system to learn Chinese. Just as learners in countries using Latin-based scripts access Chinese through familiar letters, this study proposes that Ethiopia can develop effective Chinese language learning approaches grounded in its own script tradition.

Currently, most Chinese language learning materials designed for international students are mediated through English, particularly via Latin-based scripts. For learners who do not use the Latin alphabet, this creates what may be termed “double mediation.” These learners must process Chinese through the phonetic framework of English—a system with which they may have limited or no familiarity—thereby complicating and impeding the learning process.

The experience with the Ge’ez script offers a model for preparing Chinese learning materials in other languages with indigenous scripts. Principles derived from the Ge’ez/Amharic Fidel research can serve as a foundation for similar in-depth linguistic studies worldwide, potentially transforming Chinese language education by making it accessible through learners’ native writing systems.

Thus GECH methodology—placing four tone marks directly on syllabic characters—may be systematically applied to the following scripts Japanese Kana, Korean Hangul, Yi, Cherokee, Devanagari, Bengali, Khmer, Burmese, Thai and Lao. The key is maintaining the principle that is established: one character = one syllable, with tone marks positioned where they do not interfere with existing diacritics. This research opens possibilities for transforming Chinese language education across Asia, Africa, and beyond—enabling learners to access Mandarin through their own indigenous writing systems rather than through the Latin alphabet (See annex2)

9 Research Methodology

This study employs a comparative linguistic analysis of Ge'ez/Amharic and Mandarin Chinese, examining systematic correspondences and divergences in their consonant inventories, vowel systems, tonal patterns, and syllable structures. By identifying these structural relationships, the research establishes preliminary phonetic mappings that serve as a foundation for developing a new, adapted form of the Ge'ez script tailored for representing Mandarin sounds.

The proposed writing system will extend the expressive capacity of the Ge'ez/Amharic fidel by integrating standardized tonal marking and symbols for Mandarin phonemes that do not naturally occur in Ethiopian languages. This innovation is designed to create a culturally grounded, learner-friendly orthographic bridge between the two linguistic traditions.

10 Hànyǔ Pīnyīn and Chinese Study

Pīnyīn, which literally translates to “spelled sounds,” is a phonetic system used to represent Chinese pronunciation. In this system, each syllable is constructed from two components—an initial and a final—each of which may be denoted by one or more letters. Diacritics or tone marks (̄, ́, ̂, ̌) are used to indicate the four tones found in standard Chinese language.

The Chinese Phonetic Alphabet, Hànyǔ Pīnyīn, is “China’s official system for spelling Mandarin Chinese in Roman letters. It was promulgated in 1958. By convention, practically all Chinese dictionaries compiled since then... In elementary schools in China, Pīnyīn is used as a pedagogical tool to teach students to read Chinese script” (Chen, 2016). The Pīnyīn uses 26 Roman letters and different four tone marks to represent sounds, serving as the primary method for learning Chinese pronunciation and typing characters on electronic devices.

A linguist called Zhou Youguang, who developed Pīnyīn, is named as "the father of Pīnyīn" (Odinye, 2020). Pīnyīn is also being used by Singapore and the United Nations since 1980 and 1986 respectively (O'Neill, 2023). Chinese phonology is generally described in terms of initials and finals. While initials are usually a single consonant, most finals are vowels. There are 23 initial sounds in Chinese Pīnyīn they are b, p, m, f, d, t, n, l, g, k, h, j, q, x, zh, ch, sh, r, z, c, s, y, and w (Hongwu, 2024).

Hànyǔ Pīnyīn presents its own pronunciation challenges, as learners tend to apply English sound rules to familiar letters. In Chinese language, sounds like “x” and “q” do not correspond to their English equivalents, leading to confusion. For instance, in English, “x” is pronounced as in “x-ray” (/eks/) or “exist” (/gz/), while “q” is pronounced as in “queen.” Relying on English phonics for Hànyǔ Pīnyīn creates habitual pronunciation errors that are difficult to correct later. In Chinese pronunciation “q,” is not pronounced as “kw”, rather it is pronounced as “ch”; similarly, “x” is pronounced in Chinese as “sh.” Such interference ingrains persistent mistakes that can take years to undo. In contrast, using Amharic Fidel—for example, ቺ for Qi and ጸ for Xi—bypasses the English filter entirely, enabling learners to acquire accurate Chinese pronunciation from the start.

Moreover, Pīnyīn can also use two-letter combinations to represent single sounds. This creates confusion about what constitutes a single phoneme. In the "zh," "ch," "sh" group, Chinese language learners must understand that these are not two sounds but one sound each. A new learner might try to pronounce "zh" as the "z" in "zip" followed by the "h" in "hat." Some call such confusion Pīnyīn as a "false friend" phenomenon i.e. phonetic interference (MacWhinney et al., 2005).

Pīnyīn uses a small set of vowel letters (a, o, e, i, u, ü) to represent a wider range of vowel sounds, and its spelling rules are confusing. Pīnyīn uses the letter "u" to represent two distinct vowels: /u/ (as in lu - road) and /y/ (as in lü - green) (Zhang & Zhang, 2022). Thus, while Pīnyīn is a brilliant Romanization system for typing and dictionary lookup, its major problem in teaching is that the familiar alphabet creates powerful, and often permanent, mispronunciations.

As mentioned above, the letter "x" is a perfect case study, as it exemplifies the conflict between English phonetic instinct and the distinct articulatory reality of Mandarin Chinese. Pīnyīn also doesn't help to understand Chinese character recognition and vocabulary acquisition. Because of this confusion of pronunciation mismatch between English and Hànyǔ Pīnyīn, there is a need to tell Chinese language learners explicitly on day one that they must not rely fully on the English pronunciation in using the Pīnyīn so as to avoid common errors.

11 Comparative Analysis of Geez and Mandarin Writing and Reading Systems

The Amharic Writing System

The Amharic writing system, called Fidel, is derived from the ancient Ge'ez script and is a member of the Syllabaries family. Unlike alphabetic systems where single letters represent phonemes (consonants and vowels separately), Fidel represents phonemes by combining them into units (Syllables); each character contains a consonant-vowel (CV) sequence. For instance when a stroke is added to the basic consonant "ጠ", it creates characters like "ጠጥ" (Bu), "ጠጢ" (Bi), making it hold the consonant and vowel together. In the Geez letter "ጢ" we find both "B and I" together. Similarly in a Geez letter "ጢጢ" we find three English letters "B, W and A". Since Geez uses fewer characters than Hanyu Pīnyīn, it becomes more economical in reading and writing system.

Initial Consonants Mapping:

➤ b → ጠ family	➤ q → ጥጥ family (Aspirated palatal)
➤ p → ጥጥ family	➤ x → ጥጥ family (Palatal fricative)
➤ m → ጠጠ family	➤ zh → ጥጥ family
➤ f → ጥጥ family	➤ ch → ጥጥ family (Aspirated retroflex)
➤ d → ጥጥ family	➤ sh → ጥጥ family (Retroflex fricative)
➤ t → ጥጥ family	➤ r → ጥጥ family
➤ n → ጥጥ family	➤ z → ጥጥ family
➤ l → ጥጥ family	➤ c → ጥጥ family (Aspirated alveolar)
➤ g → ጥጥ family	➤ s → ጥጥ family (Alveolar fricative)
➤ k → ጥጥ family	➤ y → ጥጥ family
➤ h → ጥጥ family	➤ w → ጥጥ family
➤ j → ጥጥ family	

Vowel Mapping:

- a: 4th or Rab'i (ጠ, ጢ, ጣ...)
- e: 5th or Hames (ጤ, ጥ, ጦ...)
- i: 3rd or Sal's (ጧ, ጨ, ጩ...)
- o: 7th or Sab'e (ጫ, ጬ, ጭ...)
- u: 2nd or Ka'eb (ጮ, ጮ, ጮ...)
- ü: 6th or close to "Sades"

This seven-vowel system gives Geez/Amharic a rich vowel inventory; this enables it to cover Mandarin vowel phonemes remarkably well.

Mandarin Final	Amharic Order	Amharic Example	Phonetic Note
a	4th (Rab'i)	ላ (La)	Open central unrounded vowel.
o	7th (Sab'e)	ሎ (Lo)	Close-mid back rounded vowel.
e	5th (Hamis)	ሌ (Le)	Mid front unrounded vowel
i	3rd (Sal's)	ሊ (Li)	Close front unrounded vowel.
u	2nd (Ka'eb)	ሉ (Lu)	Close back rounded vowel.
ü	6th (Modified-close to "Sades")	ሊኢው (L-iw)	Combines /i/ with a semivowel /w/; not a rounded vowel.

Mandarin Chinese Writing System

Standard Mandarin Chinese system is somewhat different from Geez/Amharic. Mandarin language is traditionally analyzed as "Initial" (Consonant) and "Final." Mandarin has approximately 21 initial consonants. Ge'ez Fidel has about 33 consonants. This shows that Ge'ez Fidel contains more sounds than Chinese and we understand it is capable of reading and writing Chinese in Geez Fidel.

Parallel to the vowels mentioned above, Geez has more consonants than Chinese language. Mandarin has six simple finals (vowels): a, o, e, i, u, ü. Whereas Ge'ez has seven vowels (አ፡አ፡ ኢ፡አ፡ኤ፡አ፡ኦ፡አ፡ ~ ä, u, i, a, e, ə, o). Out of these seven vowels Chinese language do not have አ(ə) and አ (ä)sound. On the other hand Geez do not have (ü) sound, which is included in the GECH Pīnyīn. Thus, by borrowing one alphabet from Chinese Pīnyīn (ü), it is possible to write Chinese in Geez.

The most distinguishing feature of the Chinese language is its word has tonal system. Four full tones and one neutral tone are used to distinguish the meaning of words. Tone 1 is high and level, Tone 2 is rising, Tone 3 is falling-rising, Tone 4 is falling. It is very interesting to note that Ge'ez has also one neutral tone (Tenebabi) and another four tones (Tenesh, Seyaf, Tetay, and Wedaqi) (Endale, 2023). There are some similarities of tones between Geez and Mandarin.

Mandarin Tone 1. This mark is represented by "-".

Mandarin Tone 2. This mark is represented by "'".

Mandarin Tone 3. This mark is represented by "v".

Mandarin Tone 4. This mark is represented by "".

We find the existence of this indigenous melodic usage very useful for Amharic speakers learning Mandarin tones. These four elements are the building blocks of the *Degua* (the book of chants). In the Ethiopian tradition, mastering these is essential for: *Qine* (Poetry): Ensuring the double meanings (*Sem ena Worq*) are delivered with the correct emphasis as well as for *Zema* (Melody): Following the notation system developed by Saint Yared, which uses these accents to guide the choir.

From this, it can be argued that a priest or language scholar who knows Ge'ez pronunciation will find it much easier to understand Chinese pronunciation and speech than someone who knows the English alphabet but do not study *kidase*-Mass in Orthodox Religion. In the Ge'ez language, the "tones" or accents (known as *Zayé*) are essential for correct pronunciation, especially in liturgical chanting and traditional poetry (*Qene*). Similar to Chinese language, changing the tone in Ge'ez can change the entire meaning.

Similarities

Both Mandarin and Geez/Amharic languages use CV structure. The Amharic seven-vowel system provides coverage for the six Mandarin simple finals.

Differences

A fundamental difference between Amharic and Mandarin phonology is the absence of tonal markers (¯, ´, ˇ, `) to indicate the four Mandarin tones. This research addresses this gap by introducing a systematic tonal marking system. Another difference lies in the presence of Chinese sounds not represented in Amharic. For example, the Mandarin sound "ü" has no equivalent in Amharic; in the GECH Pīnyīn system, this sound is incorporated as a unique symbol. Conversely, Amharic includes sounds that do not exist in Chinese, such as ጸ, ጠ, ቀ, ጪ, ጸ, ሸ, and ኘ

12 GECH Pīnyīn- Innovation to learn Chinese in Ethiopia

China has established Confucius Institutes and classrooms in Ethiopia to teach Chinese language. Similarly, Amharic language is being given in China. These will strengthen the language and cultural relationships between Ethiopia and China (Melaku (Ed.), 2025). GECH Pīnyīn has more consonants and vowels that can help Ethiopian learners to pronounce Chinese character effectively than Hànyǔ Pīnyīn. GECH provides much better phonetic notation for all Mandarin sounds, ideal for learners and teaching in Ethiopia. Unlike English, which has chaotic spelling rules, GECH Pīnyīn is entirely regular. If you learn the Geez script, you can pronounce words correctly without guessing. Unlike Geez and Mandarin pronunciation, English phonics does not have a concept of diacritic tones.

This study establishes a systematic linguistic framework for the Amharic-Chinese phonological mapping and introduces a new contribution: namely, the inclusion of tonal marking systems within the Ge'ez script writing. The research represents a significant creative work in cross-linguistic pedagogical methods and resolves the cognitive burden that Latin-based Pīnyīn systems impose on Geez letter users and Amharic speakers.

The main innovation examined in this research is the use of Geez/Amharic Fidel as a phonetic transcription system for Mandarin Chinese—a method similar to Hànyǔ Pīnyīn but operating within a writing framework familiar to Ethiopians. Mandarin has 21 initial consonants (b, p, m, f, d, t, n, l, g, k, h, j, q, x, zh, ch, sh, r, z, c, s), where as GECH has 22 basic letters (ለ, ሐ, መ, ረ, ሰ, ሸ, ቢ, ተ, ቸ, ነ, አ, ከ, ወ, ዘ, ዠ, የ, ደ, ጂ, ገ, ፈ, ፐ, /“ü” added from Latin/).

These Geez letters are selected out of 33 Consonants of Geez-some are not included because they have similar sounds like (ሀ፣ቃ) and others do not exist in Chinese language sound like ቀ, ቁ, ጠ, ጡ). The comprehensive list of Pīnyīn combinations with initials and finals across the four tones of Mandarin Pīnyīn are 2135 (See Annex 1), but GECH Pīnyīn has only 812 i.e about 62% reduction-in Pīnyīn number and study time of the language. From this figure it is clear that studying Chinese language through GECH Pīnyīn is easier than Latin Pīnyīn.

The four tones/marks are placed directly beside the Fidel to provide an immediate visual sign for the pitch, solving the "cognitive burden". For the sake of uniformity tone marks are placed immediately after the core Fidel character for all GECH Pīnyīn. This creates perfect consistency across all GECH Pīnyīn transcriptions. This standardized rule would eliminate all ambiguity, make the system visually consistent across all syllable types and make learning easier for Ethiopian language learners. Two letters are included in the GECH Pīnyīn. These are “□” and “ü”. Even if Amharic letter has the sound “ñ”, for the sake of uniformity of using “ጠ” family, modified “□” is used to represent “ñ” sound.

Similar to Chinese Hànyǔ Pīnyīn, GECH Pīnyīn has four tones plus a neutral tone. Hànyǔ Pīnyīn is built on the English alphabet and can lead to pronunciation errors because learners map English phonetics onto Chinese sounds inaccurately. There are more than 293 identified writing systems in the world. Of these, at present, around 156 are in use, as languages are becoming dead and the resulting writing systems lost (Missing Scripts Project, 2022). Considering the presence of 156 different writing systems/scripts worldwide, these indigenous scripts present viable alternatives for adapting the study of Chinese beyond the conventional Latin-based Pīnyīn system.

13 Tonal Representation Design

The most crucial technical innovation presented in this research is the system designed to represent the four tones in Mandarin Chinese within Amharic Fidel writing. This system uses special marks (diacritics) that indicate to the language learners how to raise and lower the voice without affecting the visual looks of the Fidel. This tonal representation system allows the Chinese language learners to immediately understand how to tune their voice when reading the word; this fills the largest gap seen in previous Amharic-Chinese textbooks.

Tone Design Proposal

To help learners distinguish Mandarin tones without confusion, the following design logic is proposed:

Tone	Chinese Mark	Amharic Design (e.g., "ሰ")	Design Logic
1st (Flat/High)	-	ሰ ⁻	A horizontal line above the right side of the character. Indicates a steady, high sound.
2nd (Rising)	ˊ	ሰ ^ˊ	An upward stroke on the top right. Indicates the sound rises like a question.
3rd (Falling-Rising)	ˇ	ሰ ^ˇ	A v-shape mark on the top right. Represents the dip and rise of the voice.
4th (Falling)	ˋ	ሰ ^ˋ	A downward stroke on the top right. Indicates a sharp, dropping sound.

14 GECH Pīnyīn

Basic (Neutral Tone)	1st tone (ˉ)	2nd tone (ˊ)	3rd tone (ˇ)	4th tone (ˋ)		Basic (Neutral Tone)	1st tone (ˉ)	2nd tone (ˊ)	3rd tone (ˇ)	4th tone (ˋ)
ㄐ	ㄐˉ	ㄐˊ	ㄐˇ	ㄐˋ		ǎ	ǎˉ	ǎˊ	ǎˇ	ǎˋ
ㄑ	ㄑˉ	ㄑˊ	ㄑˇ	ㄑˋ		ǎ̄	ǎ̄ˉ	ǎ̄ˊ	ǎ̄ˇ	ǎ̄ˋ
ㄒ	ㄒˉ	ㄒˊ	ㄒˇ	ㄒˋ		ǎ̇	ǎ̇ˉ	ǎ̇ˊ	ǎ̇ˇ	ǎ̇ˋ
ㄓ	ㄓˉ	ㄓˊ	ㄓˇ	ㄓˋ		ǎ̈	ǎ̈ˉ	ǎ̈ˊ	ǎ̈ˇ	ǎ̈ˋ
ㄔ	ㄔˉ	ㄔˊ	ㄔˇ	ㄔˋ		ǎ̉	ǎ̉ˉ	ǎ̉ˊ	ǎ̉ˇ	ǎ̉ˋ
ㄕ	ㄕˉ	ㄕˊ	ㄕˇ	ㄕˋ		ǎ̊	ǎ̊ˉ	ǎ̊ˊ	ǎ̊ˇ	ǎ̊ˋ
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ㄩ	ㄩˉ	ㄩˊ	ㄩˇ	ㄩˋ		ǎ̬	ǎ̬ˉ	ǎ̬ˊ	ǎ̬ˇ	ǎ̬ˋ
ㄣ	ㄣˉ	ㄣˊ	ㄣˇ	ㄣˋ		ǎ̭	ǎ̭ˉ	ǎ̭ˊ	ǎ̭ˇ	ǎ̭ˋ
ㄤ	ㄤˉ	ㄤˊ	ㄤˇ	ㄤˋ		ǎ̮	ǎ̮ˉ	ǎ̮ˊ	ǎ̮ˇ	ǎ̮ˋ
ㄨ	ㄨˉ	ㄨˊ	ㄨˇ	ㄨˋ		ǎ̯	ǎ̯ˉ	ǎ̯ˊ	ǎ̯ˇ	ǎ̯ˋ
ㄩ	ㄩˉ	ㄩˊ	ㄩˇ	ㄩˋ		ǎ̰	ǎ̰ˉ	ǎ̰ˊ	ǎ̰ˇ	ǎ̰ˋ
ㄣ	ㄣˉ	ㄣˊ	ㄣˇ	ㄣˋ		ǎ̱	ǎ̱ˉ	ǎ̱ˊ	ǎ̱ˇ	ǎ̱ˋ
ㄤ	ㄤˉ	ㄤˊ	ㄤˇ	ㄤˋ		ǎ̲	ǎ̲ˉ	ǎ̲ˊ	ǎ̲ˇ	ǎ̲ˋ
ㄨ	ㄨˉ	ㄨˊ	ㄨˇ	ㄨˋ		ǎ̳	ǎ̳ˉ	ǎ̳ˊ	ǎ̳ˇ	ǎ̳ˋ
ㄩ	ㄩˉ	ㄩˊ	ㄩˇ	ㄩˋ		ǎ̴	ǎ̴ˉ	ǎ̴ˊ	ǎ̴ˇ	ǎ̴ˋ
ㄣ	ㄣˉ	ㄣˊ	ㄣˇ	ㄣˋ		ǎ̵	ǎ̵ˉ	ǎ̵ˊ	ǎ	

Examples of writing in GECH

Mandarin-Pinyin	Phonetic Component	Meaning in Mandarin	Proposed Amharic Fidel	Tonal Mark Application	Resulting Transcription	Design Logic
mā	Initial 'm' + Final 'a'	Mother	ማ (4th/Raeb)	Tone 1: Flat/High (-)	ማ ⁻	A horizontal line above the right side of the character. Indicates a steady, high sound.
má	Initial 'm' + Final 'a'	Hemp	ማ (4th/Raeb)	Tone 2: Rising (´)	ማ [´]	An upward stroke on the top right. Indicates the sound rises like a question.
mǎ	Initial 'm' + Final 'a'	Horse	ማ (4th/Raeb)	Tone 3: Falling-Rising (ˇ)	ማ ^ˇ	A v-shape marks on the top right represents the dipping sound and rise of the voice.
mà	Initial 'm' + Final 'a'	Scold	ማ (4th/Raeb)	Tone 4: Falling (`)	ማ [`]	A downward stroke on the top right. Indicates a sharp, dropping sound.

15 Advantage of GECH Pinyin over Latin Pinyin

Comparing Latin Pinyin length with GECH Pinyin representation, the latter system consistently uses fewer characters due to its syllabic nature—each syllable is represented by a single Ge'ez character rather than multiple Latin letters.

No	Chinese Character	English Meaning	Latin Pinyin	Latin Length	GECH Pinyin	GECH Length	Letter Reduction
1)	非常感谢	thank you very much	fēi cháng gǎn xiè	14 letters	ፌ ⁻ ቻንግ ጎግ ጎግ ጎግ	7 characters	50% reduction
2)	生日快乐	happy birthday	shēng rì kuài lè	13 letters	ሼንግ ጎግ ሪ ካይ ሌ	7 characters	46.15 % reduction
3)	不好意思	sorry / excuse me	bù hǎo yì si	9 letters	ቡ ካው ጎግ ሲ	5 characters	44.44% reduction
4)	一带一路	Belt and Road Initiative	yí dài yí lù	9 letters	ዩ ዳይ ዩ ሊ	5 characters	44.44% reduction

Sample Sentence Construction Example

To illustrate the proposed system in practice, the following sample text demonstrates Amharic-script transcription with integrated tonal marking:

English: Hello, my name is Lina. I am happy to meet you.

Hanyu Pīnyīn: Nǐ hǎo, wǒ jiào Lina. Hěn gāoxìng rènshi nǐ.

GECH: ኒሕወ ዎ ጅጅዎ ሊና ኸን ን ጋዎ ሲ ንግ ረንሺ ኒ (Standardized Amharic Transcription with Tones)

In learning Chinese, Ethiopian learners face a challenge because they must learn sounds using English letters, even though they already know their own Ge'ez script. GECH Pīnyīn solves this problem by using Ge'ez characters to write Chinese sounds. Instead of using two to four English letters for one Chinese sound, GECH uses just one Ge'ez character. This makes learning faster and easier because each character stands for a whole sound, not separate pieces.

The system rests on three main ideas. First, it uses what learners already know—millions of Ethiopians already read and write Ge'ez, so they do not have to learn a new writing system just to start learning Chinese. Second, it matches one sound to one character because both Chinese sounds and Ge'ez characters join a consonant and a vowel together, creating a perfect one-to-one match. Third, it puts tone marks right on the Ge'ez character so learners see the tone and the sound together as one unit, which is much easier than looking at a separate tone mark above English letters.

A particularly significant advantage is the natural connection to Ethiopian culture. Ge'ez already has a musical tradition called *Zema*, which uses different tones for chanting. Ethiopian learners who know this tradition already understand the idea of using pitch to change meaning, so GECH connects this cultural knowledge to learning Chinese tones.

The system also makes learning easier on the mind. When using English letters, a student must see several spellings, forget how those letters sound in English, remember how they sound in Chinese, blend the letters into one sound, and then add a tone from a separate mark. With GECH,

a student only needs to see one Ge'ez character, know its sound, see the tone mark on it, and say the word. This simpler process means less confusion and faster learning.

When learning connects to what students already know, they feel more interested and motivated. They see Chinese not as something foreign and hard, but as something they can learn using their own tools. From a practical standpoint, English-based Pīnyīn has more than 2,000 possible sound combinations, while GECH has about 812—a 60 percent reduction that makes the system much easier to manage. Learners can focus on understanding Chinese instead of struggling with how to write its sounds.

Geez has also more vowels than English that helps to have more tones in reading Chinese. While GECH shows great promise, more research is still needed. Researchers should test whether individuals learn faster with GECH than with English Pīnyīn, check if they remember tones better, and reading Chinese characters faster. These studies will help make GECH even better for classroom use.

16 Basic Principles of Geez Transcription Design

This research sets out four basic principles. The first is uniformity, meaning the relationship between consonant and vowel is to be consistent and predictable. The second is economy, which involves using existing Amharic Fidel as much as possible for Chinese reading rather than creating new characters. The third is distinctiveness, which requires understanding all the differences of Mandarin Chinese sounds relative to Amharic and including the sounds. The fourth is transitionality, whereby the pronunciation method designed in Amharic should eventually replace what is seen in standard Pīnyīn and facilitate the transition to reading Chinese characters.

17 Research Agenda and Future Directions

While this research lays the foundation for an Amharic-Chinese phonetic transcription system, the following future studies must be carried out for the system to be fully implemented:

Development of books

Based on this research there is a need to prepare bilingual dictionary, training module & cultural text books that can help Chinese language learners to have additional reference materials.

Experimental Validation

Empirical experiments must be conducted on Ethiopian students/Chinese language learners to measure the effectiveness of the proposed Amharic Fidel phonetic system compared to the existing Pīnyīn system. This study will test which system allows students to identify tones and sounds faster.

Digital Tool Development

Keyboard layouts and font enhancements must be made to enable this new phonetic transcription system to be easily written on computers and phones. This will open the way for the system to be widely used in schools and on the internet.

Pedagogical Correlation with Tones

As mentioned above, using Ge'ez characters as a teaching bridge lays the foundation for designing a teaching method (Pedagogy) that enables learners to understand Chinese tones not as something new, but as an expansion of the melodic system existing in their own culture.

18 Policy Recommendations

- Linguistic experts from Ethiopia and China should collaborate on further research to strengthen Chinese language education in Ethiopia by rigorously evaluating its effectiveness through field studies and learner assessments.
- Currently, scholarship students preparing to study in China, students learning Chinese in various Ethiopian universities, Ethiopian diplomats, and Ethiopians employed in Chinese companies are all pursuing Chinese-language training. This research introduces a groundbreaking approach that uses the familiar Ge'ez script to make Chinese more accessible and intuitive for Ethiopian learners. By bridging linguistic traditions, the initiative enhances learning effectiveness while fostering deeper cultural understanding and cooperation between the two nations.
- Establish GECH Pīnyīn as a flagship model, replacing Latin-based Pīnyīn, to prioritize local writing systems worldwide, promote a culturally grounded teaching–learning process, and advance a "Decolonized Language Pedagogy."

19 Conclusion

The development of GECH Pīnyīn—a Chinese phonetic transcription system based on the Ge'ez/Amharic Fidel—represents a significant innovation in cross-linguistic pedagogy. By enabling Ethiopian learners to access Mandarin Chinese through their native writing system, this approach eliminates the "double mediation" barrier inherent in Latin-based Pīnyīn, offering a more direct, cognitively efficient path to pronunciation acquisition. This GECH Pīnyīn system allows Ethiopian learners to read Mandarin Chinese pronunciation directly through their native Ge'ez/Amharic script without the interference of English phonics.

The system's strength lies in its dual foundation: leveraging the Ge'ez/Amharic Fidel's natural syllabic structure while integrating indigenous tonal knowledge from Ethiopia's *Zema* tradition. This cultural resonance transforms tone acquisition from an abstract challenge into an extension of existing liturgical and poetic literacy, reducing cognitive load and increasing learner motivation.

Beyond pedagogical value, GECH Pīnyīn serves as a strategic tool for strengthening cultural and economic relations between Ethiopia and China, where Chinese proficiency is increasingly vital for trade, investment, and educational exchange. Its implications extend further, offering a replicable model for other nations with indigenous scripts to develop culturally grounded approaches to Chinese language education—aligning with broader movements toward decolonized pedagogy and South-South educational cooperation.

The systematic mapping presented in this study—covering 427 Mandarin syllables across four tones—provides the foundational reference for future resource development. While this innovation opens new possibilities for Amharic-medium Chinese instruction, including bilingual dictionaries and cultural textbooks, its scholarly foundation remains embryonic. Additional research is essential to validate transcription conventions, measure pedagogical effectiveness through experimental studies, and develop digital tools such as keyboard layouts and fonts.

This foundational study has outlined the linguistic principles underlying Amharic-Chinese phonological mapping, cataloged existing resources, identified critical gaps, and proposed a comprehensive research agenda. Ultimately, GECH Pīnyīn opens new possibilities for millions of Ethiopian learners to achieve Chinese language proficiency through their own cultural and linguistic heritage, while offering a transformative model for indigenous script-based language education worldwide.

20 Annex 1

Latin-GECH Pīnyīn Correspondence Table: Guide to Mandarin Tones in Geez

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
1	a	አ	ā አˉ		á አˊ		ǎ አˇ		à አˋ	
2	o	ኦ	ō ኦˉ		ó ኦˊ		ǒ ኦˇ		ò ኦˋ	
3	e	ኧ	ē ኧˉ		é ኧˊ		ě ኧˇ		è ኧˋ	
4	i	ኢ	ī ኢˉ		í ኢˊ		ǐ ኢˇ		ì ኢˋ	
5	u	ኡ	ū ኡˉ		ú ኡˊ		ǔ ኡˇ		ù ኡˋ	
6	ua	ዩዋ	uā ዩˉዋ		uá ዩˊዋ		uǎ ዩˇዋ		uà ዩˋዋ	
7	ü	ዩ	Üˉ		Üˊ		Üˇ		Üˋ	
8	ai	አይ	āi አˉይ		ái አˊይ		ǎi አˇይ		ài አˋይ	
9	ao	አዎ	āo አˉዎ		áo አˊዎ		ǎo አˇዎ		ào አˋዎ	
10	an	አን	ān አˉን		án አˊን		ǎn አˇን		àn አˋን	
11	ang	አንግ	āng አˉንግ		áng አˊንግ		ǎng አˇንግ		àng አˋንግ	
12	ei	ኧይ	ēi ኧˉይ		éi ኧˊይ		ěi ኧˇይ		èi ኧˋይ	
13	en	ኧን	ēn ኧˉን		én ኧˊን		ěn ኧˇን		èn ኧˋን	
14	eng	ኧንግ	ēng ኧˉንግ		éng ኧˊንግ		ěng ኧˇንግ		èng ኧˋንግ	
15	er	ኦር	ēr ኦˉር		ér ኦˊር		ěr ኦˇር		èr ኦˋር	
16	ou	አዎ	ōu ኦˉዎ		óu ኦˊዎ		ǒu ኦˇዎ		òu ኦˋዎ	

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
17	ong	አንግ	ōng	አˉንግ	óng	አˊንግ	ǒng	አˇንግ	òng	አˋንግ
18	ia	ኢያ	iā	ኢˉያ	íá	ኢˊያ	iǎ	ኢˇያ	ià	ኢˋያ
19	iao	ኢያው	iāo	ኢˉያው	íáo	ኢˊያው	iǎo	ኢˇያው	iào	ኢˋያው
20	ie	ኢዩ	iē	ኢˉዩ	íé	ኢˊዩ	iě	ኢˇዩ	iè	ኢˋዩ
21	iou	ኢዎዩ	iōu	ኢˉዎዩ	íou	ኢˊዎዩ	iǒu	ኢˇዎዩ	iòu	ኢˋዎዩ
22	iu	ኢዩ	iū	ኢˉዩ	íú	ኢˊዩ	iǔ	ኢˇዩ	iù	ኢˋዩ
23	ian	ኢያን	iān	ኢˉያን	ían	ኢˊያን	iǎn	ኢˇያን	iàn	ኢˋያን
24	in	ኢን	īn	ኢˉን	ín	ኢˊን	ǐn	ኢˇን	ìn	ኢˋን
25	iang	ኢያንግ	iāng	ኢˉያንግ	íang	ኢˊያንግ	iǎng	ኢˇያንግ	iàng	ኢˋያንግ
26	ing	ኢንግ	īng	ኢˉንግ	íng	ኢˊንግ	ǐng	ኢˇንግ	ìng	ኢˋንግ
27	iong	ኢዮንግ	iōng	ኢˉዮንግ	íong	ኢˊዮንግ	iǒng	ኢˇዮንግ	iòng	ኢˋዮንግ
28	üe	ኢዩዩ	üē	ኢˉዩዩ	üé	ኢˊዩዩ	üě	ኢˇዩዩ	üè	ኢˋዩዩ
29	uo	ዩዎ	uō	ዩˉዎ	uó	ዩˊዎ	uǒ	ዩˇዎ	uò	ዩˋዎ
30	uai	ዩዋይ	uāi	ዩˉዋይ	uái	ዩˊዋይ	uǎi	ዩˇዋይ	uài	ዩˋዋይ
31	uei	ዩዊ	uēi	ዩˉዊ	uéi	ዩˊዊ	uěi	ዩˇዊ	uèi	ዩˋዊ
32	uan	ዩዋን	uān	ዩˉዋን	uán	ዩˊዋን	uǎn	ዩˇዋን	uàn	ዩˋዋን

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
33	uen	ዩጢን	uēn ዩ፣ጢን		uén ዩ፣ጢን		uěn ዩ፣ጢን		uèn ዩ፣ጢን	
34	uang	ዩዋንግ	uāng ዩ፣ዋንግ		uáng ዩ፣ዋንግ		uǎng ዩ፣ዋንግ		uàng ዩ፣ዋንግ	
35	ueng	ዩውንግ	uēng ዩ፣ውንግ		uéng ዩ፣ውንግ		uěng ዩ፣ውንግ		uèng ዩ፣ውንግ	
36	üan	ኢዩዋን	üān ኢ፣ዩዋን		üán ኢ፣ዩዋን		üǎn ኢ፣ዩዋን		üàn ኢ፣ዩዋን	
37	üin	ኢዩን	üīn ኢ፣ዩን		üín ኢ፣ዩን		üǐn ኢ፣ዩን		üìn ኢ፣ዩን	
38	ba	ባ	bā ባ፣		bá ባ፣		bǎ ባ፣		bà ባ፣	
39	bo	ቦ	bō ቦ፣		bó ቦ፣		bǒ ቦ፣		bò ቦ፣	
40	bai	ባይ	bāi ባ፣ይ		bái ባ፣ይ		bǎi ባ፣ይ		bài ባ፣ይ	
41	bei	ቤይ	bēi ቤ፣ይ		béi ቤ፣ይ		běi ቤ፣ይ		bèi ቤ፣ይ	
42	bao	ባው	bāo ባ፣ው		báo ባ፣ው		bǎo ባ፣ው		bào ባ፣ው	
43	ban	ባን	bān ባ፣ን		bán ባ፣ን		bǎn ባ፣ን		bàn ባ፣ን	
44	ben	ቤን	bēn ቤ፣ን		bén ቤ፣ን		běnn ቤ፣ን		bèn ቤ፣ን	
45	bang	ባንግ	bāng ባ፣ንግ		báng ባ፣ንግ		bǎng ባ፣ንግ		bàng ባ፣ንግ	
46	beng	ቤንግ	bēng ቤ፣ንግ		béng ቤ፣ንግ		běng ቤ፣ንግ		bèng ቤ፣ንግ	
47	bi	ቢ	bī ቢ፣		bí ቢ፣		bǐ ቢ፣		bì ቢ፣	
48	bie	ቢይ	bīe ቢ፣ይ		bíe ቢ፣ይ		bǐe ቢ፣ይ		bìe ቢ፣ይ	
49	biao	ቢያው	biāo ቢ፣ያው		biáo ቢ፣ያው		biǎo ቢ፣ያው		biào ቢ፣ያው	

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
50	bian	ㄅㄧㄢˊ	biān ㄅㄧㄢˉ	ㄅㄧㄢˊ	biǎn ㄅㄧㄢˇ	ㄅㄧㄢˋ	biàn ㄅㄧㄢˋ			
51	bin	ㄅㄧㄣˊ	bīn ㄅㄧㄣˉ	bín ㄅㄧㄣˊ	bǐn ㄅㄧㄣˇ	bìn ㄅㄧㄣˋ				
52	bing	ㄅㄧㄥˊ	bīng ㄅㄧㄥˉ	bíng ㄅㄧㄥˊ	bǐng ㄅㄧㄥˇ	bìng ㄅㄧㄥˋ				
53	bu	ㄅㄨˊ	bū ㄅㄨˉ	bú ㄅㄨˊ	bǔ ㄅㄨˇ	bù ㄅㄨˋ				
54	pa	ㄆㄚˊ	pā ㄆㄚˉ	pá ㄆㄚˊ	pǎ ㄆㄚˇ	pà ㄆㄚˋ				
55	po	ㄆㄛˊ	pō ㄆㄛˉ	pó ㄆㄛˊ	pǒ ㄆㄛˇ	pò ㄆㄛˋ				
56	pai	ㄆㄞˊ	pāi ㄆㄞˉ	pái ㄆㄞˊ	pǎi ㄆㄞˇ	pài ㄆㄞˋ				
57	pei	ㄆㄟˊ	pēi ㄆㄟˉ	péi ㄆㄟˊ	pěi ㄆㄟˇ	pèi ㄆㄟˋ				
58	pao	ㄆㄞㄠˊ	pāo ㄆㄞㄠˉ	páo ㄆㄞㄠˊ	pǎo ㄆㄞㄠˇ	pào ㄆㄞㄠˋ				
59	pou	ㄆㄞㄡˊ	pōu ㄆㄞㄡˉ	póu ㄆㄞㄡˊ	pǒu ㄆㄞㄡˇ	pòu ㄆㄞㄡˋ				
60	pan	ㄆㄢˊ	pān ㄆㄢˉ	pán ㄆㄢˊ	pǎn ㄆㄢˇ	pàn ㄆㄢˋ				
61	pen	ㄆㄢˊ	pēn ㄆㄢˉ	pén ㄆㄢˊ	pěn ㄆㄢˇ	pèn ㄆㄢˋ				
62	pang	ㄆㄢˊ	pāng ㄆㄢˉ	páng ㄆㄢˊ	pǎng ㄆㄢˇ	pàng ㄆㄢˋ				
63	peng	ㄆㄥˊ	pēng ㄆㄥˉ	péng ㄆㄥˊ	pěng ㄆㄥˇ	pèng ㄆㄥˋ				
64	pi	ㄆㄧˊ	pī ㄆㄧˉ	pí ㄆㄧˊ	pǐ ㄆㄧˇ	pì ㄆㄧˋ				
65	pie	ㄆㄟˊ	piē ㄆㄟˉ	pié ㄆㄟˊ	piě ㄆㄟˇ	piè ㄆㄟˋ				
66	piao	ㄆㄞㄠˊ	piāo ㄆㄞㄠˉ	piáo ㄆㄞㄠˊ	piǎo ㄆㄞㄠˇ	piào ㄆㄞㄠˋ				
67	pian	ㄆㄧㄢˊ	piān ㄆㄧㄢˉ	pián ㄆㄧㄢˊ	piǎn ㄆㄧㄢˇ	piàn ㄆㄧㄢˋ				

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
68	pin	ፒን	pīn ፒˉን		pín ፒˊን		pǐn ፒˇን		pìn ፒˋን	
69	ping	ፒንግ	pīng ፒˉንግ		píng ፒˊንግ		pǐng ፒˇንግ		pìng ፒˋንግ	
70	pu	ፑ	pū ፑˉ		pú ፑˊ		pǔ ፑˇ		pù ፑˋ	
71	ma	ማ	mā ማˉ		má ማˊ		mǎ ማˇ		mà ማˋ	
72	mo	ሞ	mō ሞˉ		mó ሞˊ		mǒ ሞˇ		mò ሞˋ	
73	mai	ማይ	māi ማˉይ		mái ማˊይ		mǎi ማˇይ		mài ማˋይ	
74	mei	ሜይ	mēi ሜˉይ		méi ሜˊይ		měi ሜˇይ		mèi ሜˋይ	
75	mao	ማው	māo ማˉው		máo ማˊው		mǎo ማˇው		mào ማˋው	
76	mou	ሞው	mōu ሞˉው		móu ሞˊው		mǒu ሞˇው		mòu ሞˋው	
77	man	ማን	mān ማˉን		mán ማˊን		mǎn ማˇን		màn ማˋን	
78	men	ሜን	mēn ሜˉን		mén ሜˊን		mě'n ሜˇን		mèn ሜˋን	
79	mang	ማንግ	māng ማˉንግ		máng ማˊንግ		mǎng ማˇንግ		màng ማˋንግ	
80	meng	ሜንግ	mēng ሜˉንግ		méng ሜˊንግ		měng ሜˇንግ		mèng ሜˋንግ	
81	mi	ሚ	mī ሚˉ		mí ሚˊ		mǐ ሚˇ		mì ሚˋ	
82	mie	ሚይ	miē ሚˉይ		mié ሚˊይ		miě ሚˇይ		miè ሚˋይ	
83	miao	ሚያው	miāo ሚˉያው		miáo ሚˊያው		miǎo ሚˇያው		miào ሚˋያው	
84	miu	ሚዩ	miū ሚˉዩ		miú ሚˊዩ		miǔ ሚˇዩ		miù ሚˋዩ	
85	mian	ሚያን	miān ሚˉያን		mián ሚˊያን		miǎn ሚˇያን		miàn ሚˋያን	

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
86	min	ᄃᆫ	mīn ᄃᆫˉ	mín ᄃᆫˊ	mǐn ᄃᆫˊ	mìn ᄃᆫˋ				
87	ming	ᄃᆫᆫ	mīng ᄃᆫˉᆫ	míng ᄃᆫˊᆫ	mǐng ᄃᆫˊᆫ	mìng ᄃᆫˋᆫ				
88	mu	ᄃᆫ	mū ᄃᆫˉ	mú ᄃᆫˊ	mǔ ᄃᆫˊ	mù ᄃᆫˋ				
89	fa	ᄃᆫ	fā ᄃᆫˉ	fá ᄃᆫˊ	fǎ ᄃᆫˊ	fà ᄃᆫˋ				
90	fo	ᄃᆫ	fō ᄃᆫˉ	fó ᄃᆫˊ	fǒ ᄃᆫˊ	fò ᄃᆫˋ				
91	fei	ᄃᆫᆫ	fēi ᄃᆫˉᆫ	féi ᄃᆫˊᆫ	fěi ᄃᆫˊᆫ	fèi ᄃᆫˋᆫ				
92	fou	ᄃᆫᄃ	fōu ᄃᆫˉᄃ	fóu ᄃᆫˊᄃ	fǒu ᄃᆫˊᄃ	fòu ᄃᆫˋᄃ				
93	fan	ᄃᆫᆫ	fān ᄃᆫˉᆫ	fán ᄃᆫˊᆫ	fǎn ᄃᆫˊᆫ	fàn ᄃᆫˋᆫ				
94	fen	ᄃᆫᆫ	fēn ᄃᆫˉᆫ	fén ᄃᆫˊᆫ	fěn ᄃᆫˊᆫ	fèn ᄃᆫˋᆫ				
95	fang	ᄃᆫᆫᆫ	fāng ᄃᆫˉᆫᆫ	fáng ᄃᆫˊᆫᆫ	fǎng ᄃᆫˊᆫᆫ	fàng ᄃᆫˋᆫᆫ				
96	feng	ᄃᆫᆫᆫ	fēng ᄃᆫˉᆫᆫ	féng ᄃᆫˊᆫᆫ	fěng ᄃᆫˊᆫᆫ	fèng ᄃᆫˋᆫᆫ				
97	fu	ᄃᆫ	fū ᄃᆫˉ	fú ᄃᆫˊ	fǔ ᄃᆫˊ	fù ᄃᆫˋ				
98	da	ᄃᆫ	dā ᄃᆫˉ	dá ᄃᆫˊ	dǎ ᄃᆫˊ	dà ᄃᆫˋ				
99	de	ᄃᆫ	dē ᄃᆫˉ	dé ᄃᆫˊ	dě ᄃᆫˊ	dè ᄃᆫˋ				
100	dai	ᄃᆫᆫ	dāi ᄃᆫˉᆫ	dái ᄃᆫˊᆫ	dǎi ᄃᆫˊᆫ	dài ᄃᆫˋᆫ				
101	dei	ᄃᆫᆫᆫ	dēi ᄃᆫˉᆫᆫ	déi ᄃᆫˊᆫᆫ	děi ᄃᆫˊᆫᆫ	dèi ᄃᆫˋᆫᆫ				
102	dao	ᄃᆫᄃ	dāo ᄃᆫˉᄃ	dáo ᄃᆫˊᄃ	dǎo ᄃᆫˊᄃ	dào ᄃᆫˋᄃ				
103	dou	ᄃᆫᄃ	dōu ᄃᆫˉᄃ	dóu ᄃᆫˊᄃ	dǒu ᄃᆫˊᄃ	dòu ᄃᆫˋᄃ				

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
104	dan	ㄉㄢ	dān ㄉㄢˉ		dán ㄉㄢˊ		dǎn ㄉㄢˇ		dàn ㄉㄢˋ	
105	dang	ㄉㄤ	dāng ㄉㄤˉ		dáng ㄉㄤˊ		dǎng ㄉㄤˇ		dàng ㄉㄤˋ	
106	deng	ㄉㄥ	dēng ㄉㄥˉ		déng ㄉㄥˊ		děng ㄉㄥˇ		dèng ㄉㄥˋ	
107	dong	ㄉㄨㄥ	dōng ㄉㄨㄥˉ		dóng ㄉㄨㄥˊ		dǒng ㄉㄨㄥˇ		dòng ㄉㄨㄥˋ	
108	di	ㄉㄧ	dī ㄉㄧˉ		dí ㄉㄧˊ		dǐ ㄉㄧˇ		dì ㄉㄧˋ	
109	die	ㄉㄧㄝ	diē ㄉㄧㄝˉ		dié ㄉㄧㄝˊ		diě ㄉㄧㄝˇ		diè ㄉㄧㄝˋ	
110	diao	ㄉㄧㄠ	diāo ㄉㄧㄠˉ		diáo ㄉㄧㄠˊ		diǎo ㄉㄧㄠˇ		diào ㄉㄧㄠˋ	
111	diu	ㄉㄧㄡ	diū ㄉㄧㄡˉ		diú ㄉㄧㄡˊ		diǔ ㄉㄧㄡˇ		diù ㄉㄧㄡˋ	
112	dian	ㄉㄧㄢ	diān ㄉㄧㄢˉ		dián ㄉㄧㄢˊ		diǎn ㄉㄧㄢˇ		diàn ㄉㄧㄢˋ	
113	ding	ㄉㄧㄥ	dīng ㄉㄧㄥˉ		díng ㄉㄧㄥˊ		dǐng ㄉㄧㄥˇ		dìng ㄉㄧㄥˋ	
114	du	ㄉㄨ	dū ㄉㄨˉ		dú ㄉㄨˊ		dǔ ㄉㄨˇ		dù ㄉㄨˋ	
115	duo	ㄉㄨㄛ	duō ㄉㄨㄛˉ		duó ㄉㄨㄛˊ		duǒ ㄉㄨㄛˇ		duò ㄉㄨㄛˋ	
116	dui	ㄉㄨㄟ	duī ㄉㄨㄟˉ		duí ㄉㄨㄟˊ		duǐ ㄉㄨㄟˇ		duì ㄉㄨㄟˋ	
117	duan	ㄉㄨㄢ	duān ㄉㄨㄢˉ		duán ㄉㄨㄢˊ		duǎn ㄉㄨㄢˇ		duàn ㄉㄨㄢˋ	
118	dun	ㄉㄨㄢ	dūn ㄉㄨㄢˉ		dún ㄉㄨㄢˊ		dǔn ㄉㄨㄢˇ		dùn ㄉㄨㄢˋ	
119	ta	ㄊㄚ	tā ㄊㄚˉ		tá ㄊㄚˊ		tǎ ㄊㄚˇ		tà ㄊㄚˋ	
120	te	ㄊㄜ	tē ㄊㄜˉ		té ㄊㄜˊ		tě ㄊㄜˇ		tè ㄊㄜˋ	
121	tai	ㄊㄞ	tāi ㄊㄞˉ		tái ㄊㄞˊ		tǎi ㄊㄞˇ		tài ㄊㄞˋ	

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
122	tao	ㄊㄠˊ	tāo	ㄊㄠˉ	táo	ㄊㄠˊ	tǎo	ㄊㄠˇ	tào	ㄊㄠˋ
123	tou	ㄊㄡˊ	tōu	ㄊㄡˉ	tóu	ㄊㄡˊ	tǒu	ㄊㄡˇ	tòu	ㄊㄡˋ
124	tan	ㄊㄢˊ	tān	ㄊㄢˉ	tán	ㄊㄢˊ	tǎn	ㄊㄢˇ	tàn	ㄊㄢˋ
125	tang	ㄊㄤˊ	tāng	ㄊㄤˉ	táng	ㄊㄤˊ	tǎng	ㄊㄤˇ	tàng	ㄊㄤˋ
126	teng	ㄊㄥˊ	tēng	ㄊㄥˉ	téng	ㄊㄥˊ	těng	ㄊㄥˇ	tèng	ㄊㄥˋ
127	tong	ㄊㄨㄥˊ	tōng	ㄊㄨㄥˉ	tóng	ㄊㄨㄥˊ	tǒng	ㄊㄨㄥˇ	tòng	ㄊㄨㄥˋ
128	ti	ㄊㄧˊ	tī	ㄊㄧˉ	tí	ㄊㄧˊ	tǐ	ㄊㄧˇ	tì	ㄊㄧˋ
129	tie	ㄊㄧㄝˊ	tiē	ㄊㄧㄝˉ	tié	ㄊㄧㄝˊ	tiě	ㄊㄧㄝˇ	tiè	ㄊㄧㄝˋ
130	tiao	ㄊㄧㄠˊ	tiāo	ㄊㄧㄠˉ	tiáo	ㄊㄧㄠˊ	tiǎo	ㄊㄧㄠˇ	tiào	ㄊㄧㄠˋ
131	tian	ㄊㄧㄢˊ	tiān	ㄊㄧㄢˉ	tián	ㄊㄧㄢˊ	tiǎn	ㄊㄧㄢˇ	tiàn	ㄊㄧㄢˋ
132	ting	ㄊㄧㄥˊ	tīng	ㄊㄧㄥˉ	tíng	ㄊㄧㄥˊ	tǐng	ㄊㄧㄥˇ	tìng	ㄊㄧㄥˋ
133	tu	ㄊㄨˊ	tū	ㄊㄨˉ	tú	ㄊㄨˊ	tǔ	ㄊㄨˇ	tù	ㄊㄨˋ
134	tuo	ㄊㄨㄛˊ	tuō	ㄊㄨㄛˉ	tuó	ㄊㄨㄛˊ	tuǒ	ㄊㄨㄛˇ	tuò	ㄊㄨㄛˋ
135	tui	ㄊㄨㄟˊ	tuī	ㄊㄨㄟˉ	tuí	ㄊㄨㄟˊ	tuǐ	ㄊㄨㄟˇ	tuì	ㄊㄨㄟˋ
136	tuan	ㄊㄨㄢˊ	tuān	ㄊㄨㄢˉ	tuán	ㄊㄨㄢˊ	tuǎn	ㄊㄨㄢˇ	tuàn	ㄊㄨㄢˋ
137	tun	ㄊㄨㄣˊ	tūn	ㄊㄨㄣˉ	tún	ㄊㄨㄣˊ	tǔn	ㄊㄨㄣˇ	tùn	ㄊㄨㄣˋ
138	na	ㄋㄚˊ	nā	ㄋㄚˉ	ná	ㄋㄚˊ	nǎ	ㄋㄚˇ	nà	ㄋㄚˋ
139	ne	ㄋㄝˊ	nē	ㄋㄝˉ	né	ㄋㄝˊ	ně	ㄋㄝˇ	nè	ㄋㄝˋ

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
140	nai	ናይ	nāi	ናˉይ	nái	ናˊይ	nǎi	ናˇይ	nài	ናˋይ
141	nei	ኔይ	nēi	ኔˉይ	néi	ኔˊይ	něi	ኔˇይ	nèi	ኔˋይ
142	nao	ናኦ	nāo	ናˉኦ	náo	ናˊኦ	nǎo	ናˇኦ	nào	ናˋኦ
143	nou	ኖው	nōu	ኖˉው	nóu	ኖˊው	nǒu	ኖˇው	nòu	ኖˋው
144	nan	ናን	nān	ናˉን	nán	ናˊን	nǎn	ናˇን	nàn	ናˋን
145	nen	ኔን	nēn	ኔˉን	nén	ኔˊን	něnn	ኔˇን	nèn	ኔˋን
146	nang	ናንግ	nāng	ናˉንግ	náng	ናˊንግ	nǎng	ናˇንግ	nàng	ናˋንግ
147	neng	ኔንግ	nēng	ኔˉንግ	néng	ኔˊንግ	něng	ኔˇንግ	nèng	ኔˋንግ
148	nong	ኖንግ	nōng	ኖˉንግ	nóng	ኖˊንግ	nǒng	ኖˇንግ	nòng	ኖˋንግ
149	ni	ኒ	nī	ኒˉ	ní	ኒˊ	nǐ	ኒˇ	nì	ኒˋ
150	nie	ኒዩ	niē	ኒˉዩ	nié	ኒˊዩ	niě	ኒˇዩ	niè	ኒˋዩ
151	niao	ኒዮኦ	niāo	ኒˉዮኦ	niáo	ኒˊዮኦ	niǎo	ኒˇዮኦ	niào	ኒˋዮኦ
152	niu	ኒዩ	niū	ኒˉዩ	niú	ኒˊዩ	niǔ	ኒˇዩ	niù	ኒˋዩ
153	nian	ኒዮን	niān	ኒˉዮን	nián	ኒˊዮን	niǎn	ኒˇዮን	niàn	ኒˋዮን
154	nin	ኒን	nīn	ኒˉን	nín	ኒˊን	nǐn	ኒˇን	nìn	ኒˋን
155	niang	ኒዮንግ	niāng	ኒˉዮንግ	niáng	ኒˊዮንግ	niǎng	ኒˇዮንግ	niàng	ኒˋዮንግ
156	ning	ኒንግ	nīng	ኒˉንግ	níng	ኒˊንግ	nǐng	ኒˇንግ	nìng	ኒˋንግ
157	nu	ኑ	nū	ኑˉ	nú	ኑˊ	nǔ	ኑˇ	nù	ኑˋ

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
158	nuo	ኖ	nuō	ኖˉ	nuó	ኖˊ	nuǒ	ኖˇ	nuò	ኖˋ
159	nuan	ኑዋን	nuān	ኑˉዋን	nuán	ኑˊዋን	nuǎn	ኑˇዋን	nuàn	ኑˋዋን
160	nü	ኒኢው	nū	ኒˉኢው	nú	ኒˊኢው	nǔ	ኒˇኢው	nù	ኒˋኢው
161	nüe	ኒኢዩ	nüē	ኒˉኢዩ	nüé	ኒˊኢዩ	nüě	ኒˇኢዩ	nüè	ኒˋኢዩ
162	la	ላ	lā	ላˉ	lá	ላˊ	lǎ	ላˇ	là	ላˋ
163	le	ሌ	lē	ሌˉ	lé	ሌˊ	lě	ሌˇ	lè	ሌˋ
164	lai	ላይ	lāi	ላˉይ	lái	ላˊይ	lǎi	ላˇይ	lài	ላˋይ
165	lei	ሌይ	lēi	ሌˉይ	léi	ሌˊይ	lěi	ሌˇይ	lèi	ሌˋይ
166	lao	ላው	lāo	ላˉው	láo	ላˊው	lǎo	ላˇው	lào	ላˋው
167	lou	ሎው	lōu	ሎˉው	lóu	ሎˊው	lǒu	ሎˇው	lòu	ሎˋው
168	lan	ላን	lān	ላˉን	lán	ላˊን	lǎn	ላˇን	làn	ላˋን
169	lang	ላንግ	lāng	ላˉንግ	láng	ላˊንግ	lǎng	ላˇንግ	làng	ላˋንግ
170	leng	ሌንግ	lēng	ሌˉንግ	léng	ሌˊንግ	lěng	ሌˇንግ	lèng	ሌˋንግ
171	long	ሎንግ	lōng	ሎˉንግ	lóng	ሎˊንግ	lǒng	ሎˇንግ	lòng	ሎˋንግ
172	li	ሊ	lī	ሊˉ	lí	ሊˊ	lǐ	ሊˇ	lì	ሊˋ
173	lia	ሊያ	liā	ሊˉያ	liá	ሊˊያ	liǎ	ሊˇያ	lià	ሊˋያ
174	lie	ሊዩ	liē	ሊˉዩ	lié	ሊˊዩ	liě	ሊˇዩ	liè	ሊˋዩ
175	liao	ሊያኦ	liāo	ሊˉያኦ	liáo	ሊˊያኦ	liǎo	ሊˇያኦ	liào	ሊˋያኦ

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
176	liu	ㄌㄩˊ	liū ㄌㄩˊ		liú ㄌㄩˊ		liǔ ㄌㄩˇ		liù ㄌㄩˋ	
177	lian	ㄌㄩㄢˋ	liān ㄌㄩㄢˋ		lián ㄌㄩㄢˊ		liǎn ㄌㄩㄢˇ		liàn ㄌㄩㄢˋ	
178	lin	ㄌㄩㄣˋ	līn ㄌㄩㄣˋ		lín ㄌㄩㄣˊ		lǐn ㄌㄩㄣˇ		lìn ㄌㄩㄣˋ	
179	liang	ㄌㄩㄤˋ	liāng ㄌㄩㄤˋ		liáng ㄌㄩㄤˊ		liǎng ㄌㄩㄤˇ		liàng ㄌㄩㄤˋ	
180	ling	ㄌㄩㄥˋ	līng ㄌㄩㄥˋ		líng ㄌㄩㄥˊ		lǐng ㄌㄩㄥˇ		lìng ㄌㄩㄥˋ	
181	lu	ㄌㄨˊ	lū ㄌㄨˊ		lú ㄌㄨˊ		lǔ ㄌㄨˇ		lù ㄌㄨˋ	
182	luo	ㄌㄨㄛˊ	luō ㄌㄨㄛˊ		luó ㄌㄨㄛˊ		luǒ ㄌㄨㄛˇ		luò ㄌㄨㄛˋ	
183	luan	ㄌㄨㄢˋ	luān ㄌㄨㄢˋ		luán ㄌㄨㄢˊ		luǎn ㄌㄨㄢˇ		luàn ㄌㄨㄢˋ	
184	lun	ㄌㄨㄣˋ	lūn ㄌㄨㄣˋ		lún ㄌㄨㄣˊ		lǔn ㄌㄨㄣˇ		lùn ㄌㄨㄣˋ	
185	lü	ㄌㄩˊ	lū ㄌㄩˊ		lú ㄌㄩˊ		lǔ ㄌㄩˇ		lù ㄌㄩˋ	
186	lüe	ㄌㄩㄝˊ	lüē ㄌㄩㄝˊ		lüé ㄌㄩㄝˊ		lüě ㄌㄩㄝˇ		lüè ㄌㄩㄝˋ	
187	ga	ㄍㄚˊ	gā ㄍㄚˊ		gá ㄍㄚˊ		gǎ ㄍㄚˇ		gà ㄍㄚˋ	
188	ge	ㄍㄜˊ	gē ㄍㄜˊ		gé ㄍㄜˊ		gě ㄍㄜˇ		gè ㄍㄜˋ	
189	gai	ㄍㄞˊ	gāi ㄍㄞˊ		gái ㄍㄞˊ		gǎi ㄍㄞˇ		gài ㄍㄞˋ	
190	gei	ㄍㄟˊ	gēi ㄍㄟˊ		géi ㄍㄟˊ		gěi ㄍㄟˇ		gèi ㄍㄟˋ	
191	gao	ㄍㄠˊ	gāo ㄍㄠˊ		gáo ㄍㄠˊ		gǎo ㄍㄠˇ		gào ㄍㄠˋ	
192	gou	ㄍㄡˊ	gōu ㄍㄡˊ		góu ㄍㄡˊ		gǒu ㄍㄡˇ		gòu ㄍㄡˋ	
193	gan	ㄍㄢˋ	gān ㄍㄢˋ		gán ㄍㄢˋ		gǎn ㄍㄢˇ		gàn ㄍㄢˋ	

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
194	gen	ጌን	gēn ጌˉን		gén ጌˊን		gěń ጌˇን		gèn ጌˋን	
195	gang	ጋንግ	gāng ጋˉንግ		gáng ጋˊንግ		gǎng ጋˇንግ		gàng ጋˋንግ	
196	geng	ጌንግ	gēng ጌˉንግ		géng ጌˊንግ		gěng ጌˇንግ		gèng ጌˋንግ	
197	gong	ጎንግ	gōng ጎˉንግ		góng ጎˊንግ		gǒng ጎˇንግ		gòng ጎˋንግ	
198	gu	ጉ	gū ጉˉ		gú ጉˊ		gǔ ጉˇ		gù ጉˋ	
199	gua	ጻ	guā ጻˉ		guá ጻˊ		guǎ ጻˇ		guà ጻˋ	
200	guo	ጎ	guō ጎˉ		guó ጎˊ		guǒ ጎˇ		guò ጎˋ	
201	guai	ጻይ	guāi ጻˉይ		guái ጻˊይ		guǎi ጻˇይ		guài ጻˋይ	
202	gui	ጉይ	guī ጉˉይ		guí ጉˊይ		guǐ ጉˇይ		guì ጉˋይ	
203	guan	ጻን	guān ጻˉን		guán ጻˊን		guǎn ጻˇን		guàn ጻˋን	
204	gun	ጉን	gūn ጉˉን		gún ጉˊን		gǔn ጉˇን		gùn ጉˋን	
205	guang	ጻንግ	guāng ጻˉንግ		guáng ጻˊንግ		guǎng ጻˇንግ		guàng ጻˋንግ	
206	ka	ካ	kā ካˉ		ká ካˊ		kǎ ካˇ		kà ካˋ	
207	ke	ኬ	kē ኬˉ		ké ኬˊ		kě ኬˇ		kè ኬˋ	
208	kai	ካይ	kāi ካˉይ		kái ካˊይ		kǎi ካˇይ		kài ካˋይ	
209	kei	ኬይ	kēi ኬˉይ		kéi ኬˊይ		kěi ኬˇይ		kèi ኬˋይ	
210	kao	ካዎ	kāo ካˉዎ		káo ካˊዎ		kǎo ካˇዎ		kào ካˋዎ	
211	kou	ኮዎ	kōu ኮˉዎ		kóu ኮˊዎ		kǒu ኮˇዎ		kòu ኮˋዎ	

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
212	kan	ካን	kān ካˉን		kán ካˊን		kǎn ካˇን		kàn ካˋን	
213	ken	ኬን	kēn ኬˉን		kén ኬˊን		kěn ኬˇን		kèn ኬˋን	
214	kang	ካንግ	kāng ካˉንግ		káng ካˊንግ		kǎng ካˇንግ		kàng ካˋንግ	
215	keng	ኬንግ	kēng ኬˉንግ		kéng ኬˊንግ		kěng ኬˇንግ		kèng ኬˋንግ	
216	kong	ኮንግ	kōng ኮˉንግ		kóng ኮˊንግ		kǒng ኮˇንግ		kòng ኮˋንግ	
217	ku	ኪ	kū ኪˉ		kú ኪˊ		kǔ ኪˇ		kù ኪˋ	
218	kua	ኪ	kuā ኪˉ		kuá ኪˊ		kuǎ ኪˇ		kuà ኪˋ	
219	kuo	ኪ	kuō ኪˉ		kuó ኪˊ		kuǒ ኪˇ		kuò ኪˋ	
220	kuai	ኪይ	kuāi ኪˉይ		kuái ኪˊይ		kuǎi ኪˇይ		kuài ኪˋይ	
221	kui	ኪይ	kuī ኪˉይ		kuí ኪˊይ		kuǐ ኪˇይ		kui ኪˋይ	
222	kuan	ኪን	kuān ኪˉን		kuán ኪˊን		kuǎn ኪˇን		kuàn ኪˋን	
223	kun	ኪን	kūn ኪˉን		kún ኪˊን		kǔn ኪˇን		kùn ኪˋን	
224	kuang	ኪንግ	kuāng ኪˉንግ		kuáng ኪˊንግ		kuǎng ኪˇንግ		kuàng ኪˋንግ	
225	ha	ከ	hā ከˉ		há ከˊ		hǎ ከˇ		hà ከˋ	
226	he	ኬ	hē ኬˉ		hé ኬˊ		hě ኬˇ		hè ኬˋ	
227	hai	ከይ	hāi ከˉይ		hái ከˊይ		hǎi ከˇይ		hài ከˋይ	
228	hei	ኬይ	hēi ኬˉይ		héi ኬˊይ		hěi ኬˇይ		hèi ኬˋይ	
229	hao	ከዎ	hāo ከˉዎ		háo ከˊዎ		hǎo ከˇዎ		hào ከˋዎ	

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˊ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
230	hou	ㄏㄡˊ	hōu	ㄏㄡˊ	hóu	ㄏㄡˊ	hǒu	ㄏㄡˇ	hòu	ㄏㄡˋ
231	han	ㄏㄢˋ	hān	ㄏㄢˋ	hán	ㄏㄢˋ	hǎn	ㄏㄢˇ	hàn	ㄏㄢˋ
232	hen	ㄏㄣˋ	hēn	ㄏㄣˋ	hén	ㄏㄣˋ	hěn	ㄏㄣˇ	hèn	ㄏㄣˋ
233	hang	ㄏㄤˋ	hāng	ㄏㄤˋ	háng	ㄏㄤˋ	hǎng	ㄏㄤˇ	hàng	ㄏㄤˋ
234	heng	ㄏㄥˋ	hēng	ㄏㄥˋ	héng	ㄏㄥˋ	hěng	ㄏㄥˇ	hèng	ㄏㄥˋ
235	hong	ㄏㄨㄥˋ	hōng	ㄏㄨㄥˋ	hóng	ㄏㄨㄥˋ	hǒng	ㄏㄨㄥˇ	hòng	ㄏㄨㄥˋ
236	hu	ㄏㄨˊ	hū	ㄏㄨˊ	hú	ㄏㄨˊ	hǔ	ㄏㄨˇ	hù	ㄏㄨˋ
237	hua	ㄏㄨㄚˊ	huā	ㄏㄨㄚˊ	huá	ㄏㄨㄚˊ	huǎ	ㄏㄨㄚˇ	huà	ㄏㄨㄚˋ
238	huo	ㄏㄨㄛˊ	huō	ㄏㄨㄛˊ	huó	ㄏㄨㄛˊ	huǒ	ㄏㄨㄛˇ	huò	ㄏㄨㄛˋ
239	huai	ㄏㄨㄞˊ	huāi	ㄏㄨㄞˊ	huái	ㄏㄨㄞˊ	huǎi	ㄏㄨㄞˇ	huài	ㄏㄨㄞˋ
240	hui	ㄏㄨㄞˊ	huī	ㄏㄨㄞˊ	huí	ㄏㄨㄞˊ	huǐ	ㄏㄨㄞˇ	huì	ㄏㄨㄞˋ
241	huan	ㄏㄨㄢˋ	huān	ㄏㄨㄢˋ	huán	ㄏㄨㄢˋ	huǎn	ㄏㄨㄢˇ	huàn	ㄏㄨㄢˋ
242	hun	ㄏㄨㄣˋ	hūn	ㄏㄨㄣˋ	hún	ㄏㄨㄣˋ	hǔn	ㄏㄨㄣˇ	hùn	ㄏㄨㄣˋ
243	huang	ㄏㄨㄤˋ	huāng	ㄏㄨㄤˋ	huáng	ㄏㄨㄤˋ	huǎng	ㄏㄨㄤˇ	huàng	ㄏㄨㄤˋ
244	ji	ㄐㄧˊ	jī	ㄐㄧˊ	jí	ㄐㄧˊ	jǐ	ㄐㄧˇ	jì	ㄐㄧˋ
245	jia	ㄐㄧㄚˊ	jiā	ㄐㄧㄚˊ	jiá	ㄐㄧㄚˊ	jiǎ	ㄐㄧㄚˇ	jià	ㄐㄧㄚˋ
246	jiao	ㄐㄧㄠˊ	jiāo	ㄐㄧㄠˊ	jiáo	ㄐㄧㄠˊ	jiǎo	ㄐㄧㄠˇ	jiào	ㄐㄧㄠˋ
247	jie	ㄐㄧㄝˊ	jiē	ㄐㄧㄝˊ	jié	ㄐㄧㄝˊ	jiě	ㄐㄧㄝˇ	jiè	ㄐㄧㄝˋ

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
248	jiu	ㄐㄡ	jiū ㄐㄡˉ		jiú ㄐㄡˊ		jiǔ ㄐㄡˇ		jiù ㄐㄡˋ	
249	jian	ㄐㄢ	jiān ㄐㄢˉ		jián ㄐㄢˊ		jiǎn ㄐㄢˇ		jiàn ㄐㄢˋ	
250	jin	ㄐㄣ	jīn ㄐㄣˉ		jín ㄐㄣˊ		jǐn ㄐㄣˇ		jìn ㄐㄣˋ	
251	jiang	ㄐㄨㄥ	jiāng ㄐㄨㄥˉ		jiáng ㄐㄨㄥˊ		jiǎng ㄐㄨㄥˇ		jiàng ㄐㄨㄥˋ	
252	jing	ㄐㄩㄥ	jīng ㄐㄩㄥˉ		jíng ㄐㄩㄥˊ		jǐng ㄐㄩㄥˇ		jìng ㄐㄩㄥˋ	
253	jiong	ㄐㄨㄥ	jiōng ㄐㄨㄥˉ		jióng ㄐㄨㄥˊ		jiǒng ㄐㄨㄥˇ		jiòng ㄐㄨㄥˋ	
254	ju	ㄐㄩ	jū ㄐㄩˉ		jú ㄐㄩˊ		jǔ ㄐㄩˇ		jù ㄐㄩˋ	
255	jue	ㄐㄨㄝ	juē ㄐㄨㄝˉ		jué ㄐㄨㄝˊ		juě ㄐㄨㄝˇ		juè ㄐㄨㄝˋ	
256	juan	ㄐㄨㄢ	juān ㄐㄨㄢˉ		juán ㄐㄨㄢˊ		juǎn ㄐㄨㄢˇ		juàn ㄐㄨㄢˋ	
257	jun	ㄐㄨㄣ	jūn ㄐㄨㄣˉ		jún ㄐㄨㄣˊ		jǔn ㄐㄨㄣˇ		jùn ㄐㄨㄣˋ	
258	qi	ㄑㄩ	qī ㄑㄩˉ		qí ㄑㄩˊ		qǐ ㄑㄩˇ		qì ㄑㄩˋ	
259	qia	ㄑㄩㄚ	qiā ㄑㄩㄚˉ		qiá ㄑㄩㄚˊ		qiǎ ㄑㄩㄚˇ		qià ㄑㄩㄚˋ	
260	qiao	ㄑㄩㄠ	qiāo ㄑㄩㄠˉ		qiáo ㄑㄩㄠˊ		qiǎo ㄑㄩㄠˇ		qiào ㄑㄩㄠˋ	
261	qie	ㄑㄩㄝ	qiē ㄑㄩㄝˉ		qié ㄑㄩㄝˊ		qiě ㄑㄩㄝˇ		qiè ㄑㄩㄝˋ	
262	qiu	ㄑㄩㄟ	qiū ㄑㄩㄟˉ		qiú ㄑㄩㄟˊ		qiǔ ㄑㄩㄟˇ		qiù ㄑㄩㄟˋ	
263	qian	ㄑㄩㄢ	qiān ㄑㄩㄢˉ		qián ㄑㄩㄢˊ		qiǎn ㄑㄩㄢˇ		qiàn ㄑㄩㄢˋ	
264	qin	ㄑㄩㄣ	qīn ㄑㄩㄣˉ		qín ㄑㄩㄣˊ		qǐn ㄑㄩㄣˇ		qìn ㄑㄩㄣˋ	
265	qiang	ㄑㄩㄥ	qiāng ㄑㄩㄥˉ		qiáng ㄑㄩㄥˊ		qiǎng ㄑㄩㄥˇ		qiàng ㄑㄩㄥˋ	

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
266	qing	ቺንግ	qīng	ቺ፡ንግ	qíng	ቺ፡ንግ	qǐng	ቺ፡ንግ	qìng	ቺ፡ንግ
267	qiong	ቺዮንግ	qiōng	ቺ፡ዮንግ	qióng	ቺ፡ዮንግ	qiǒng	ቺ፡ዮንግ	qiòng	ቺ፡ዮንግ
268	qu	ቺ	qū	ቺ፡	qú	ቺ፡	qǔ	ቺ፡	qù	ቺ፡
269	que	ቺዬ	quē	ቺ፡ዬ	qué	ቺ፡ዬ	quě	ቺ፡ዬ	què	ቺ፡ዬ
270	quan	ቺዋን	quān	ቺ፡ዋን	quán	ቺ፡ዋን	quǎn	ቺ፡ዋን	quàn	ቺ፡ዋን
271	qun	ቺን	qūn	ቺ፡ን	qún	ቺ፡ን	qǔn	ቺ፡ን	qùn	ቺ፡ን
272	xi	ሺ	xī	ሺ፡	xí	ሺ፡	xǐ	ሺ፡	xì	ሺ፡
273	xia	ሻ	xiā	ሻ፡	xiá	ሻ፡	xiǎ	ሻ፡	xià	ሻ፡
274	xiao	ሻው	xiāo	ሻ፡ው	xiáo	ሻ፡ው	xiǎo	ሻ፡ው	xiào	ሻ፡ው
275	xie	ሺ	xiē	ሺ፡	xié	ሺ፡	xiě	ሺ፡	xiè	ሺ፡
276	xiu	ሺዬ	xiū	ሺ፡ዬ	xiú	ሺ፡ዬ	xiǔ	ሺ፡ዬ	xiù	ሺ፡ዬ
277	xian	ሻን	xiān	ሻ፡ን	xián	ሻ፡ን	xiǎn	ሻ፡ን	xiàn	ሻ፡ን
278	xin	ሺን	xīn	ሺ፡ን	xín	ሺ፡ን	xǐn	ሺ፡ን	xìn	ሺ፡ን
279	xiang	ሺያንግ	xiāng	ሺ፡ያንግ	xiáng	ሺ፡ያንግ	xiǎng	ሺ፡ያንግ	xiàng	ሺ፡ያንግ
280	xing	ሺንግ	xīng	ሺ፡ንግ	xíng	ሺ፡ንግ	xǐng	ሺ፡ንግ	xìng	ሺ፡ንግ
281	xiong	ሺዮንግ	xiōng	ሺ፡ዮንግ	xióng	ሺ፡ዮንግ	xiǒng	ሺ፡ዮንግ	xiòng	ሺ፡ዮንግ
282	xu	ሺ	xū	ሺ፡	xú	ሺ፡	xǔ	ሺ፡	xù	ሺ፡
283	xue	ሺዬ	xuē	ሺ፡ዬ	xué	ሺ፡ዬ	xuě	ሺ፡ዬ	xuè	ሺ፡ዬ

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˊ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
284	xuan	ጽዋን	xuān ጽ፡፡ን		xuán ጽ፡፡ን		xuǎn ጽ፡፡ን		xuàn ጽ፡፡ን	
285	xun	ጽን	xūn ጽ፡፡ን		xún ጽ፡፡ን		xǔn ጽ፡፡ን		xùn ጽ፡፡ን	
286	zha	ገ	zhā ገ፡፡		zhá ገ፡፡		zhǎ ገ፡፡		zhà ገ፡፡	
287	zhe	ገፍ	zhē ገ፡፡ፍ		zhé ገ፡፡ፍ		zhě ገ፡፡ፍ		zhè ገ፡፡ፍ	
288	zhi	ገፍ	zhī ገ፡፡ፍ		zhí ገ፡፡ፍ		zhǐ ገ፡፡ፍ		zhì ገ፡፡ፍ	
289	zhai	ገፍይ	zhāi ገ፡፡ይ		zhái ገ፡፡ይ		zhǎi ገ፡፡ይ		zhài ገ፡፡ይ	
290	zhei	ገፍይ	zhēi ገ፡፡ይ		zhéi ገ፡፡ይ		zhěi ገ፡፡ይ		zhèi ገ፡፡ይ	
291	zhao	ገፍኦ	zhāo ገ፡፡ኦ		zháo ገ፡፡ኦ		zhǎo ገ፡፡ኦ		zhào ገ፡፡ኦ	
292	zhou	ገፍው	zhōu ገ፡፡ው		zhóu ገ፡፡ው		zhǒu ገ፡፡ው		zhòu ገ፡፡ው	
293	zhan	ገፍን	zhān ገ፡፡ን		zhán ገ፡፡ን		zhǎn ገ፡፡ን		zhàn ገ፡፡ን	
294	zhen	ገፍን	zhēn ገ፡፡ን		zhén ገ፡፡ን		zhěn ገ፡፡ን		zhèn ገ፡፡ን	
295	zhang	ገፍንግ	zhāng ገ፡፡ንግ		zháng ገ፡፡ንግ		zhǎng ገ፡፡ንግ		zhàng ገ፡፡ንግ	
296	zheng	ገፍንግ	zhēng ገ፡፡ንግ		zhéng ገ፡፡ንግ		zhěng ገ፡፡ንግ		zhèng ገ፡፡ንግ	
297	zhong	ገፍንግ	zhōng ገ፡፡ንግ		zhóng ገ፡፡ንግ		zhǒng ገ፡፡ንግ		zhòng ገ፡፡ንግ	
298	zhu	ገፍ	zhū ገ፡፡		zhú ገ፡፡		zhǔ ገ፡፡		zhù ገ፡፡	
299	zhua	ገፍጥ	zhuā ገ፡፡ጥ		zhuá ገ፡፡ጥ		zhuǎ ገ፡፡ጥ		zhuà ገ፡፡ጥ	
300	zhuo	ገፍ	zhuō ገ፡፡		zhuó ገ፡፡		zhuǒ ገ፡፡		zhuò ገ፡፡	
301	zhuai	ገፍጥይ	zhuāi ገ፡፡ጥይ		zhuái ገ፡፡ጥይ		zhuǎi ገ፡፡ጥይ		zhuài ገ፡፡ጥይ	

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
302	zhui	ገፍይ	zhuī ገፍˉይ		zhuí ገፍˊይ		zhuǐ ገፍˇይ		zhùi ገፍˋይ	
303	zhuan	ገፍዋን	zhuān ገፍˉዋን		zhuán ገፍˊዋን		zhuǎn ገፍˇዋን		zhuàn ገፍˋዋን	
304	zhun	ገፍን	zhūn ገፍˉን		zhún ገፍˊን		zhǔn ገፍˇን		zhùn ገፍˋን	
305	zhuang	ገፍዋንግ	zhuāng ገፍˉዋንግ		zhuáng ገፍˊዋንግ		zhuǎng ገፍˇዋንግ		zhuàng ገፍˋዋንግ	
306	cha	ቻ	chā ቻˉ		chá ቻˊ		chǎ ቻˇ		chà ቻˋ	
307	che	ቼ	chē ቼˉ		ché ቼˊ		chě ቼˇ		chè ቼˋ	
308	chi	ቸ	chī ቸˉ		chí ቸˊ		chǐ ቸˇ		chì ቸˋ	
309	chai	ቻይ	chāi ቻˉይ		chái ቻˊይ		chǎi ቻˇይ		chài ቻˋይ	
310	chao	ቻኦ	chāo ቻˉኦ		cháo ቻˊኦ		chǎo ቻˇኦ		chào ቻˋኦ	
311	chou	ቻው	chōu ቻˉው		chóu ቻˊው		chǒu ቻˇው		chòu ቻˋው	
312	chan	ቻን	chān ቻˉን		chán ቻˊን		chǎn ቻˇን		chàn ቻˋን	
313	chen	ቼን	chēn ቼˉን		chén ቼˊን		chěn ቼˇን		chèn ቼˋን	
314	chang	ቻንግ	chāng ቻˉንግ		cháng ቻˊንግ		chǎng ቻˇንግ		chàng ቻˋንግ	
315	cheng	ቼንግ	chēng ቼˉንግ		chéng ቼˊንግ		chěng ቼˇንግ		chèng ቼˋንግ	
316	chong	ቻንግ	chōng ቻˉንግ		chóng ቻˊንግ		chǒng ቻˇንግ		chòng ቻˋንግ	
317	chu	ቸ	chū ቸˉ		chú ቸˊ		chǔ ቸˇ		chù ቸˋ	
318	chua	ቸዋ	chuā ቸˉዋ		chuá ቸˊዋ		chuǎ ቸˇዋ		chuà ቸˋዋ	
319	chuo	ቸ	chuō ቸˉ		chuó ቸˊ		chuǒ ቸˇ		chuò ቸˋ	

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
320	chuai	ቸዋይ	chuāi ፳፻፱		chuái ፳፻፱		chuǎi ፳፻፱		chuài ፳፻፱	
321	chui	ቸይ	chuī ፳፻፱		chuí ፳፻፱		chuǐ ፳፻፱		chuì ፳፻፱	
322	chuan	ቸዋን	chuān ፳፻፱		chuán ፳፻፱		chuǎn ፳፻፱		chuàn ፳፻፱	
323	chun	ቸን	chūn ፳፻፱		chún ፳፻፱		chǔn ፳፻፱		chùn ፳፻፱	
324	chuang	ቸዋንግ	chuāng ፳፻፱ግ		chuáng ፳፻፱ግ		chuǎng ፳፻፱ግ		chuàng ፳፻፱ግ	
325	sha	ሻ	shā ሻˉ		shá ሻˊ		shǎ ሻˇ		shà ሻˋ	
326	she	ሼ	shē ሼˉ		shé ሼˊ		shě ሼˇ		shè ሼˋ	
327	shi	ሺ	shī ሺˉ		shí ሺˊ		shǐ ሺˇ		shì ሺˋ	
328	shai	ሻይ	shāi ሻˉይ		shái ሻˊይ		shǎi ሻˇይ		shài ሻˋይ	
329	shei	ሼይ	shēi ሼˉይ		shéi ሼˊይ		shěi ሼˇይ		shèi ሼˋይ	
330	shao	ሻኦ	shāo ሻˉኦ		sháo ሻˊኦ		shǎo ሻˇኦ		shào ሻˋኦ	
331	shou	ሻው	shōu ሻˉው		shóu ሻˊው		shǒu ሻˇው		shòu ሻˋው	
332	shan	ሻን	shān ሻˉን		shán ሻˊን		shǎn ሻˇን		shàn ሻˋን	
333	shen	ሼን	shēn ሼˉን		shén ሼˊን		shěn ሼˇን		shèn ሼˋን	
334	shang	ሻንግ	shāng ሻˉንግ		sháng ሻˊንግ		shǎng ሻˇንግ		shàng ሻˋንግ	
335	sheng	ሼንግ	shēng ሼˉንግ		shéng ሼˊንግ		shěng ሼˇንግ		shèng ሼˋንግ	
336	shu	ሻ	shū ሻˉ		shú ሻˊ		shǔ ሻˇ		shù ሻˋ	
337	shua	ሻዋ	shuā ሻˉዋ		shuá ሻˊዋ		shuǎ ሻˇዋ		shuà ሻˋዋ	

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
338	shuo	ሹ	shuō ˉ		shuó ˊ		shuǒ ˇ		shuò ˋ	
339	shuai	ሹፂ	shuāi ˉ		shuái ˊ		shuǎi ˇ		shuài ˋ	
340	shui	ሹይ	shuǐ ˉ		shuí ˊ		shuǐ ˇ		shuì ˋ	
341	shuan	ሹፎን	shuān ˉ		shuán ˊ		shuǎn ˇ		shuàn ˋ	
342	shun	ሹን	shūn ˉ		shún ˊ		shǔn ˇ		shùn ˋ	
343	shuang	ሹፎንግ	shuāng ˉ		shuáng ˊ		shuǎng ˇ		shuàng ˋ	
344	re	ሬ	rē ˉ		ré ˊ		rě ˇ		rè ˋ	
345	ri	ሬ	rī ˉ		rí ˊ		rǐ ˇ		rì ˋ	
346	rao	ሬዎ	rāo ˉ		ráo ˊ		rǎo ˇ		rào ˋ	
347	rou	ሬዎ	rōu ˉ		róu ˊ		rǒu ˇ		ròu ˋ	
348	ran	ሬን	rān ˉ		rán ˊ		rǎn ˇ		ràn ˋ	
349	ren	ሬን	rēn ˉ		rén ˊ		rěn ˇ		rèn ˋ	
350	rang	ሬንግ	rāng ˉ		ráng ˊ		rǎng ˇ		ràng ˋ	
351	reng	ሬንግ	rēng ˉ		réng ˊ		rěng ˇ		rèng ˋ	
352	rong	ሬንግ	rōng ˉ		róng ˊ		rǒng ˇ		ròng ˋ	
353	ru	ሩ	rū ˉ		rú ˊ		rǔ ˇ		rù ˋ	
354	ruo	ሮ	ruō ˉ		ruó ˊ		ruǒ ˇ		ruò ˋ	
355	rui	ሩይ	rūi ˉ		rúi ˊ		rǔi ˇ		rùi ˋ	

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˊ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
356	ruan	ሩዋን	ruān	ሩˊዋን	ruán	ሩˊዋን	ruǎn	ሩˇዋን	ruàn	ሩˋዋን
357	run	ሩን	rūn	ሩˊን	rún	ሩˊን	rǔn	ሩˇን	rùn	ሩˋን
358	za	ዛ	zā	ዛˊ	zá	ዛˊ	zǎ	ዛˇ	zà	ዛˋ
359	ze	ዜ	zē	ዜˊ	zé	ዜˊ	zě	ዜˇ	zè	ዜˋ
360	zi	ዘ	zī	ዘˊ	zí	ዘˊ	zǐ	ዘˇ	zì	ዘˋ
361	zai	ዛይ	zāi	ዛˊይ	zái	ዛˊይ	zǎi	ዛˇይ	zài	ዛˋይ
362	zao	ዛኦ	zāo	ዛˊኦ	záo	ዛˊኦ	zǎo	ዛˇኦ	zào	ዛˋኦ
363	zou	ዘው	zōu	ዘˊው	zóu	ዘˊው	zǒu	ዘˇው	zòu	ዘˋው
364	zan	ዛን	zān	ዛˊን	zán	ዛˊን	zǎn	ዛˇን	zàn	ዛˋን
365	zen	ዜን	zēn	ዜˊን	zén	ዜˊን	zěnn	ዜˇን	zèn	ዜˋን
366	zang	ዛንግ	zāng	ዛˊንግ	záng	ዛˊንግ	zǎng	ዛˇንግ	zàng	ዛˋንግ
367	zeng	ዜንግ	zēng	ዜˊንግ	zéng	ዜˊንግ	zěng	ዜˇንግ	zèng	ዜˋንግ
368	zong	ዘንግ	zōng	ዘˊንግ	zóng	ዘˊንግ	zǒng	ዘˇንግ	zòng	ዘˋንግ
369	zu	ዙ	zū	ዙˊ	zú	ዙˊ	zǔ	ዙˇ	zù	ዙˋ
370	zuo	ዙ	zuō	ዙˊ	zuó	ዙˊ	zuǒ	ዙˇ	zuò	ዙˋ
371	zui	ዙይ	zuī	ዙˊይ	zuí	ዙˊይ	zuǐ	ዙˇይ	zuì	ዙˋይ
372	zuan	ዙዋን	zuān	ዙˊዋን	zuán	ዙˊዋን	zuǎn	ዙˇዋን	zuàn	ዙˋዋን
373	zun	ዙን	zūn	ዙˊን	zún	ዙˊን	zǔn	ዙˇን	zùn	ዙˋን

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
374	ca ń (Alveola raspira ted)	ń	cā ńˉ		cá ńˊ		că ńˇ		cà ńˋ	
375	ce	ĕ	cē ĕˉ		cé ĕˊ		cě ĕˇ		cè ĕˋ	
376	ci	ĭ	cī ĭˉ		cí ĭˊ		cǐ ĭˇ		cì ĭˋ	
377	cai	ńĕ	cāi ńˉĕ		cái ńˊĕ		căi ńˇĕ		cài ńˋĕ	
378	cao	ńw	cāo ńˉw		cáo ńˊw		căo ńˇw		cào ńˋw	
379	cou	ńw	cōu ńˉw		cóu ńˊw		cǒu ńˇw		còu ńˋw	
380	can	ńʒ	cān ńˉʒ		cán ńˊʒ		căn ńˇʒ		càn ńˋʒ	
381	cen	ńʒ	cēn ńˉʒ		cén ńˊʒ		cěn ńˇʒ		cèn ńˋʒ	
382	cang	ńʒŋ	cāng ńˉʒŋ		cáng ńˊʒŋ		căng ńˇʒŋ		càng ńˋʒŋ	
383	ceng	ńʒŋ	cēng ńˉʒŋ		céng ńˊʒŋ		cěng ńˇʒŋ		cèng ńˋʒŋ	
384	cong	ńʒŋ	cōng ńˉʒŋ		cóng ńˊʒŋ		cǒng ńˇʒŋ		còng ńˋʒŋ	
385	cu	ń	cū ńˉ		cú ńˊ		cǔ ńˇ		cù ńˋ	
386	cuo	ń	cuō ńˉ		cuó ńˊ		cuǒ ńˇ		cuò ńˋ	
387	cui	ńĕ	cūi ńˉĕ		cúi ńˊĕ		cǔi ńˇĕ		cùi ńˋĕ	
388	cuan	ńwʒ	cuān ńˉwʒ		cuán ńˊwʒ		cuǎn ńˇwʒ		cuàn ńˋwʒ	
389	cun	ńʒ	cūn ńˉʒ		cún ńˊʒ		cǔn ńˇʒ		cùn ńˋʒ	
390	Sa ń (Alveolar fricative)	ń	sā ńˉ		sá ńˊ		să ńˇ		sà ńˋ	

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
391	se	ḥ	sē ḥˉ		sé ḥˊ		sě ḥˇ		sè ḥˋ	
392	si	ḥ	sī ḥˉ		sí ḥˊ		sǐ ḥˇ		sì ḥˋ	
393	sai	ḥḗ	sāi ḥˉḗ		sái ḥˊḗ		sǎi ḥˇḗ		sài ḥˋḗ	
394	sao	ḥḡ	sāo ḥˉḡ		sáo ḥˊḡ		sǎo ḥˇḡ		sào ḥˋḡ	
395	sou	ḥḡ	sōu ḥˉḡ		sóu ḥˊḡ		sǒu ḥˇḡ		sòu ḥˋḡ	
396	san	ḥḗ	sān ḥˉḗ		sán ḥˊḗ		sǎn ḥˇḗ		sàn ḥˋḗ	
397	sen	ḥḗ	sēn ḥˉḗ		sén ḥˊḗ		sěn ḥˇḗ		sèn ḥˋḗ	
398	sang	ḥḗḡ	sāng ḥˉḗḡ		sáng ḥˊḗḡ		sǎng ḥˇḗḡ		sàng ḥˋḗḡ	
399	seng	ḥḗḡ	sēng ḥˉḗḡ		séng ḥˊḗḡ		sěng ḥˇḗḡ		sèng ḥˋḗḡ	
400	song	ḥḗḡ	sōng ḥˉḗḡ		sóng ḥˊḗḡ		sǒng ḥˇḗḡ		sòng ḥˋḗḡ	
401	su	ḥ	sū ḥˉ		sú ḥˊ		sǔ ḥˇ		sù ḥˋ	
402	suo	ḥ	suō ḥˉ		suó ḥˊ		suǒ ḥˇ		suo ḥˋ	
403	sui	ḥḗ	suī ḥˉḗ		suí ḥˊḗ		suǐ ḥˇḗ		sui ḥˋḗ	
404	suan	ḥḡḗ	suān ḥˉḡḗ		suán ḥˊḡḗ		suǎn ḥˇḡḗ		suàn ḥˋḡḗ	
405	sun	ḥḗ	sūn ḥˉḗ		sún ḥˊḗ		sǔn ḥˇḗ		sùn ḥˋḗ	
406	yi	ḥ	yī ḥˉ		yí ḥˊ		yǐ ḥˇ		yì ḥˋ	
407	ya	ḥ	yā ḥˉ		yá ḥˊ		yǎ ḥˇ		yà ḥˋ	
408	yao	ḥḡ	yāo ḥˉḡ		yáo ḥˊḡ		yǎo ḥˇḡ		yào ḥˋḡ	

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
409	ye	ㄝ	yē ㄝˉ		yé ㄝˊ		yě ㄝˇ		yè ㄝˋ	
410	you	ㄩ	yōu ㄩˉ		yóu ㄩˊ		yǒu ㄩˇ		yòu ㄩˋ	
411	yan	ㄢ	yān ㄢˉ		yán ㄢˊ		yǎn ㄢˇ		yàn ㄢˋ	
412	yang	ㄢㄍ	yāng ㄢˉㄍ		yáng ㄢˊㄍ		yǎng ㄢˇㄍ		yàng ㄢˋㄍ	
413	ying	ㄢㄍㄩ	yīng ㄢˉㄍㄩ		yíng ㄢˊㄍㄩ		yǐng ㄢˇㄍㄩ		yìng ㄢˋㄍㄩ	
414	yong	ㄢㄍㄩㄥ	yōng ㄩㄥˉ		yóng ㄩㄥˊ		yǒng ㄩㄥˇ		yòng ㄩㄥˋ	
415	yu	ㄩ	yū ㄩˉ		yú ㄩˊ		yǔ ㄩˇ		yù ㄩˋ	
416	yue	ㄩㄝ	yuē ㄩㄝˉ		yué ㄩㄝˊ		yuě ㄩㄝˇ		yuè ㄩㄝˋ	
417	yuan	ㄩㄢ	yuān ㄩㄢˉ		yuán ㄩㄢˊ		yuǎn ㄩㄢˇ		yuàn ㄩㄢˋ	
418	yun	ㄩㄢ	yūn ㄩㄢˉ		yún ㄩㄢˊ		yǔn ㄩㄢˇ		yùn ㄩㄢˋ	
419	wu	ㄨ	wū ㄨˉ		wú ㄨˊ		wǔ ㄨˇ		wù ㄨˋ	
420	wa	ㄨㄚ	wā ㄨㄚˉ		wá ㄨㄚˊ		wǎ ㄨㄚˇ		wà ㄨㄚˋ	
421	wo	ㄨㄛ	wō ㄨㄛˉ		wó ㄨㄛˊ		wǒ ㄨㄛˇ		wò ㄨㄛˋ	
422	wai	ㄨㄞ	wāi ㄨㄞˉ		wái ㄨㄞˊ		wǎi ㄨㄞˇ		wài ㄨㄞˋ	
423	wei	ㄨㄟ	wēi ㄨㄟˉ		wéi ㄨㄟˊ		wěi ㄨㄟˇ		wèi ㄨㄟˋ	
424	wan	ㄨㄢ	wān ㄨㄢˉ		wán ㄨㄢˊ		wǎn ㄨㄢˇ		wàn ㄨㄢˋ	

No	Basic/ Neutral Tone		Tone1 (ˉ)		Tone2 (ˊ)		Tone3 (ˇ)		Tone4 (ˋ)	
	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH	Latin	GECH
425	wen	འཇ	wēn	འཇˉ	wén	འཇˊ	wěn	འཇˇ	wèn	འཇˋ
426	wang	འཇལ	wāng	འཇˉལ	wáng	འཇˊལ	wǎng	འཇˇལ	wàng	འཇˋལ
427	weng	འཇལ	wēng	འཇˉལ	wéng	འཇˊལ	wěng	འཇˇལ	wèng	འཇˋལ

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